

Deliverable 2.1

ROBIN Regional Governance Models

CTA
June 2023

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

Funded by
the European Union

PROJECT INFORMATION

PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON-CSA
PROJECT NUMBER	101060504
START DAY	1 September 2022
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	ROBIN Regional Governance Models
WORK PACKAGE	WP2
TASK	T2.1
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DATE	June 2023

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public, fully open	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Changes	Responsible partner
0.1	20/06/2023	Initial content with inputs from regional nodes submitted for quality review	CTA
0.2	26/06/2023	Consortium and quality review	All partners
0.3	28/06/2023	Final content	CTA
2	30/06/2023	Final version was submitted to the EC	QPL

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1. INTRODUCTION.....	9
Objective of ROBIN.....	9
Objective of Work package 2.....	10
Objective of Task 2.1 and the co-creation events	10
2. REGIONAL EVENTS METHODOLOGY	10
Official event title.....	13
Workshop main objective	13
Agenda.....	13
Registration and venue	14
Required equipment, support materials, logistics	14
Attendees	15
Mail to be sent after the event	16
3. REGIONAL EVENTS ORGANIZATION.....	17
Andalusia regional event	17
<i>Andalusian regional event organization</i>	<i>17</i>
<i>Andalusian regional governance model.....</i>	<i>28</i>
Baden-Württemberg regional event.....	35
<i>Baden-Württemberg regional event organization.....</i>	<i>35</i>
<i>Baden-Württemberg regional governance model.....</i>	<i>44</i>
Central Macedonia regional event	48
<i>Central Macedonia regional event organization</i>	<i>48</i>
<i>Macedonia regional governance model</i>	<i>56</i>
Southern Region regional event	61
<i>Southern Region regional event organization</i>	<i>61</i>
<i>Southern Region, Ireland regional governance model</i>	<i>68</i>
Žilina regional event	73
<i>Žilina regional event organization</i>	<i>73</i>
<i>Žilina regional governance model</i>	<i>84</i>
4. CONCLUSIONS	90
5. ANNEXES	93

Annex 1: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Workshop Guide 93

Annex 2 - Baseline questionnaire97

Annex 3 – Scheme of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework 100

Annex 4 - List of actions of the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework..... 101

Annex 5 - Satisfaction survey template..... 103

Annex 6 - Official agenda Central Macedonia workshop..... 104

Annex 7 - Central Macedonia Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas 105

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework 11

Figure 2. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas template (up) and pre-filled (down) 12

Figure 3. Regional event infoday 15

Figure 4. Save-the-date for the Andalusian regional event 17

Figure 5. CANVAS in poster size 18

Figure 6. Original agenda 19

Figure 7. Picture of the event venue..... 20

Figure 8. Workshop participants 21

Figure 9. Welcome from the organisers to the participants. 22

Figure 10. Andalusia Baseline presentation 24

Figure 11. Andalusia potential of biomass presentation..... 25

Figure 12. Andalusia SWOT presentation 25

Figure 13. Regional Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework presentation 26

Figure 14. Andalusia Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model CANVAS pre-filled..... 27

Figure 15. Satisfaction survey results..... 27

Figure 16. Prioritisation of the strategic areas of the RCBMF for Andalusia 31

Figure 17. Andalusia Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model CANVAS 34

Figure 18. Picture of the session in Stuttgart, Germany..... 36

Figure 19. Baden-Württemberg baseline presentation..... 38

Figure 20. Empty CANVAS used in the first session (in which "Aufgaben" means Jobs and "Schmerzen" means Pains)..... 39

Figure 21. CANVAS resulting from the first session (in orange are "Jobs", in blue "Pains" and in green "Value propositions") 40

Figure 22. Part of the governance model CANVAS (2nd value proposition: Matchmaking and partner search) 43

Figure 23. Governance model CANVAS (1st value proposition: Policy framework) 43

Figure 24. Official invitation of ROBIN Region of Central Macedonia Co-creation Workshop 48

Figure 25. Central Macedonia agenda 49

Figure 26. Some of the workshop attendees at the closing of the event 50

Figure 27. Baseline Monitoring Survey-presenting Mentimeter results..... 52

Figure 28. ROBIN project introduction and regional context for Region of Central Macedonia 53

Figure 29. Working sessions on biomass feedstocks	54
Figure 30. Working sessions on co-creation framework and CANVAS	55
Figure 31. Official agenda.....	62
Figure 32. Workshop attendees	62
Figure 33. ROBIN workshop in progress.....	62
Figure 34. Southern Region baseline presentation	64
Figure 35. ROBIN workshop in progress.....	66
Figure 36. ROBIN workshop in progress.....	67
Figure 37. ROBIN workshop in progress.....	68
Figure 38. Southern Region of Ireland Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas	72
Figure 39. Save-the-date for the ZSK regional event.....	73
Figure 40. Moments from the co-creation workshop in Žilina region	74
Figure 41. Žilina Baseline monitoring results	82
Figure 42. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas resulting from the co-creation workshop in the Žilina Region.....	89
Figure 43. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Workshop Guide	93
Figure 44. EU Bioeconomy Pillars.....	93
Figure 45. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Work Draft Canvas.....	94
Figure 46. Scheme of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework	100
Figure 47. Official agenda Central Macedonia workshop.....	104
Figure 48. Central Macedonia Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas	105

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Consortium partners	9
Table 2. Translation of the most important contributions to the CANVAS of the first session	40
Table 3. Main key barriers and/or challenges identified in the first session	44
Table 4. Central Macedonia baseline results	51
Table 5. Main workshops results	91

ABBREVIATIONS

CBGMC	Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas
CLLD	Community-Led Local Development
DoA	Description of the action
ESDP	Economic and Strategic Development Program
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key performance indicator
LAGs	Local Action Groups
MARCs	Multi-Actor Regional Constellations
QH	Quadruple Helix
RCBGMF	Regional Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework
RRAs	Regional Development Agencies
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents main results from Task 2.1 - Co-creating the Regional Governance Models and Practices with Key Stakeholders.

The aim of this task was to actively engage the Multi-Actor Regional Constellations (MARC)s, and other relevant regional stakeholders, in the co-creation of specific governance models and practices that overcome barriers and seize opportunities for circular bioeconomy in the ROBIN regions.

For this purpose, specific ROBIN tools were designed and used, as the Regional Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework (RCBGMF) and the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas (CBGMC), using the event as a first tool testing.

Each ROBIN region engaged the regional MARC members and additional actors from the quadruple helix to participate in the co-creative workshops, comprising the following sessions:

Session 1: Validation and prioritization of key barriers, potentialities and opportunities to be pursued.

Session 2: Definition of improvement areas for current governance model(s) & co-creation of new one(s).

In total, five workshops have been held, one in each region, with 69 participants, including MARC members as well as other regional quadruple helix stakeholders:

- 15 policy makers,
- 17 researchers and academics,
- 12 civil society representatives,
- 23 business and SME representatives.
- 2 Other

Each region has identified a value proposition and created a new or improved regional governance model linked to it, to work in and transform into a business model during the next work package activity (T2.2.), when dedicated action plans will be developed, including social activities and measures among others, considering typologies of governance models and good practices gathered in ROBIN deliverables D1.1. and D1.2, respectively.

All the work performed at regional level has followed a two-fold approach:

- Observing common and agreed general indications to guarantee that the workshops' main objectives were reached,
- Adapting the content and co-creation experience to each region maturity level and specific needs (including information about the regional situation framework, resource available and SWOT analysis)

The development of the co-creation activities were nurtured by the results obtained in ROBIN's work package 1, especially by the Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models (D1.1.) and its Governance Models Typology Matrix, and the Good Governance Practices (D1.2.)

In general, and according to the satisfaction surveys' results, the workshops were evaluated very positively from the attendees, with high marks in all categories.

1. Introduction

Objective of ROBIN

The main aim of the ROBIN project is to empower Europe's Regions to adapt their governance models and structures to accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts. Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of just, inclusive, and resilient economic development for their territories. To this end, we establish and demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 European Regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. ROBIN will provide them with all the necessary support for networking and mutual learning, as well as a practical digital Toolbox to drive the operation of successful governance models. We will closely monitor and evaluate the project's performance, providing evidence of its economic, societal, and environmental impacts.

To this end, the consortium of ROBIN brings together a complementary and interdisciplinary group of 12 partners and 1 affiliated entity across 6 different countries within the European Union (EU), as presented in the Table 1.

Table 1. Consortium partners

Partner Role*	Partner No	Partner Name	Partner Short name	Country
CO	1	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	QPL	Greece
CR	2	FUNDACION CORPORACION TECNOLOGICA DE ANDALUCIA	CTA	Spain
CR	3	WHITE RESEARCH SPRL	WR	Belgium
CR	4	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PED	Slovakia
CR	5	STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	S2I	Germany
CR	6	ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	ZSK	Slovakia
CR	7	MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	MTU	Ireland
CR	8	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Greece
CR	9	REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	RCM	Greece
CR	10	CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	CAP	Spain
AE	10.1	INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACIÓN Y FORMACIÓN AGRARIA, PESQUERA, ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCIÓN ECOLÓGICA	IFA	Spain
CR	11	BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTEMBERG GMBH	BPRO	Germany
CR	12	SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	SRA	Ireland

* CO = Coordinator, CR = Contractor, AE = Affiliated Entities

To ensure that ROBIN delivers on its aim to deploy circular bioeconomies at regional level with a territorial approach, 5 diverse EU regions are engaged as partners within the project. These regions are:

- Andalucía, Spain
- Baden-Württemberg, Germany
- Central Macedonia, Greece
- Southern Region, Ireland
- Zilina, Slovakia

Objective of Work package 2

WP2 has a two-fold approach:

- 1) Co-creating tailored circular bioeconomy governance models and structures with the active involvement of the key actors within each of ROBIN's regions, and
- 2) Design the ROBIN toolbox.

The specific objectives of WP2 are:

- Co-create, new and improved governance models and practices.
- Design and develop the ROBIN tools to guide the integration of regional opportunities.
- Define the appropriate support actions and a plan for providing support in each region.
- Aggregate the project's tools and services for the implementation of sustainable value chains.

Objective of Task 2.1 and the co-creation events

Specifically, task 2.1 aims at actively engaging the regional ecosystems (mainly through the MARC members and other QH stakeholders) in the co-creation of governance models and practices that could overcome barriers and seize opportunities for circular bioeconomy at regional level.

T2.1 main objectives are:

- To conduct co-creation activities engaging the MARCs and other relevant stakeholders
- Gather information on key barriers, potentialities and opportunities to be pursued.
- Definition of improvement areas for current governance model(s) & co-creation of new one(s).

2. Regional events methodology

To guarantee a common event structure, while allowing some flexibility according to the regional needs, some preliminary event guidelines were provided considering that:

- Each regional node (composed by at least two project partners in each case) was responsible of formatting the agenda, inviting attendees, disseminating the event and taking care of the registration process and satisfaction survey feedback gathering.
- Regarding communication of the event, each partner should have taken the lead on this. ROBIN social media would supported event dissemination when possible.

The primary ROBIN tools used in the workshops were:

- the **RCBGMF**: A primary aim of the ROBIN project is regional governance model development, with this in mind a framework with regional considerations was developed. Along with the categories outlined by the EU Bioeconomy Strategy, a further 3 categories were included within the framework based on the regional considerations: Social Benefits, Environmental Benefits, and Regional Benefits. The RCBGMF (Figure 1) was used by the regional nodes to prioritise regional needs and/or identify the regional value proposition to work with in the CBGMC.

Figure 1. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework

- the **CBGMC**: one of the key tools of the future ROBIN toolbox, that can support the regions in developing and updating their circular bioeconomy governance models, comprises elements such as the improved/new governance model's value proposition, beneficiaries, activities, partnerships, infrastructure and resources, cost structure and sustainability related costs and benefits. The CBGMC was used in the workshops for defining the regional value proposition, identify activities to be included in the regional support action plans (to be further developed in T2.2.), as well as shaping relevant aspects of the improved/new governance models per region. They also provided us prompts for novel business models and social measures to be further developed within the project. A CBGMC template was prepared, as well as a pre-filled example based on the Andalusian region case Figure 2. Additionally, a dedicated CBGMC guidelines document was performed aimed at training all the partners in the proper use of the tool (see Annex 1).

Figure 2. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas template (up) and pre-filled (down)

Official event title

As a general recommendation the title would include « ROBIN regional event ». Regional nodes could add any additional subtitle if desired/needed.

Workshop main objective

Actively engage MARCs and other relevant regional stakeholders **in the co-creation of specific governance models and practices that overcome barriers and seize opportunities for the circular bioeconomy in each region.**

Agenda

The agenda should follow the same outline and include at least the following 2 sessions:

- Session 1: Presentation and discussion of the regional analysis, including barriers and opportunities:
 - Presentation of the bioeconomy regional governance model background (situation of the model in the specific region to understand where the region wants to arrive)
 - Description if available, or co-creation session with participants, to identify the most relevant biomass feedstocks of the region.
 - Presentation of the SWOT analysis performed by the ROBIN regional node, to be discussed and fine-tuned with the participants.

- Session 2: Co-definition of improvement areas for current governance model(s) & co-creation of new one(s), using the stakeholder management methodology to manage actors' diverse interests, leveraging their unique perspectives to cross-fertilise initial ideas and co-define with them the governance models:
 - Prioritization of top regional support pre-selected actions, based on the Governance Model Co-Creation Framework
 - Hands-on working session on the CBGMC

Based on this, an example of a tentative agenda was provided:

- Introduction session:
 - Attendants welcome, brief presentation of the ROBIN project and main objectives of the workshop
 - Warm-up interactive session based on the baseline monitoring survey.
- Session 1: Presentation and discussion of the regional analysis:
 - Presentation of the bioeconomy regional governance model background (situation of the model in the specific region to understand where the region wants to arrive)
 - Description if available, or co-creation session with participants, to identify the most relevant biomass feedstocks of the region.
 - Presentation of the SWOT analysis performed by the ROBIN regional node, to be discussed and fine-tuned with the participants.
- Session 2: Definition of improvement areas for current governance model(s) & co-creation of new one(s):

- Prioritization of top regional support pre-selected actions, based on the Governance Model Co-Creation Framework
- Hands-on working session on the CBGMC
- Wrap-up session and information about ROBIN next steps and actions planned at regional level (the aim of this slot is to briefly introduce the validation exercise so stakeholders can be aware of that in case their participation might be needed at a later stage).
- Lunch or cocktail networking

The event could be done in local language (preferred) or in English. For the project presentation, the one prepared by the project communication leader (WR) was available at project intranet, as well as any other dissemination and communication relevant material can be used.

Registration and venue

Registration was done by the regional node host using their usual platforms and procedures. All data were managed according to the FAIR principles and good data management practices as well as ROBIN ethical guidelines for personal data and recruiting volunteers, which are GDPR compliant, avoid transferring personal data amongst partners. It was recommended to ask the attendees for the following information:

- Name
- Gender
- e-mail
- Company
- Position

If done face-to-face, it is always advisable to ask the attendee if he/she will participate in the coffee or cocktail networking and if there are any allergies to consider.

Concerning the venue, it was advisable to organise the event as a face-to-face event, being at the discretion of the regional node partners to select the most suitable location in terms of available budget and event needs.

Required equipment, support materials, logistics

After the event, the presentations used and ROBIN brochures etc. were to be sent to attendees by email, together with a satisfaction survey.

In case the event was done face-to-face, coffee, or cocktail catering, name tags, project communication material (ROBIN brochures) and participant package were to be provided. As for the participant package, this would include a copy of all the presentations used during the event and corporate communication materials from the regional partners as desired. The satisfaction survey had to be shared among participants at the end of the event as hard copy and sent by email to those that had not answered. For justification purposes, a signature sheet was prepared and circulated among participants during the event.

In case the event was done online, each host could decide the most suitable platform for such purpose.

All the communication materials linked to the project such as brochure could be downloaded from project intranet.

Before or during the event, a monitoring baseline survey linked to the monitoring work package of the project (WP4) was shared among the participants. It was provided by PEDAL (WP4 leader) and can be found in Annex 2.

It was strongly recommended to develop templates prefilled by the regional node to have a basis on which build on and discuss during the workshops for the SWOT analysis and the CBGMC model.

The internal preparation work included also an internal regional events infoday on the 30th of March, allowing all the partner to ask any question may have regarding the guidelines document (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Regional event infoday

Attendees

The main target audience of the regional co-creation events are the regional MARC members, although some other relevant regional stakeholders could also be invited.

Each regional event had an internal KPI of 10 attendees (without considering the project partners). Each regional node was responsible for selecting the most suitable profiles and persons among their corresponding MARC, guaranteeing a well-balanced combination of profiles from the quadruple helix if possible.

It was recommended to leverage on speaker organisations that could support the host in the event dissemination efforts. An example of the email for inviting MARC members was provided, in order to allow partners to adapt it to the local language, etc.

Dear Mr./Ms.:

[name of host] is participating in the ROBIN project (<https://robin-project.eu/>), funded by the European Commission. This project aims to empower Europe's regions to adapt their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts.

In the frame of this project and given your expertise in the field, we invite you to participate in the [Final name of the event], where you can hear in detail about the project and will participate in a co-creation exercise to discuss about main regional needs, challenges, potential solutions, etc.

This event will take place **face-to-face/online on xxxx from xxxh to xxh**.

The planned programme is as follows: [it can be inserted here as text or the link to the online agenda can be provided]

Please feel free to register here [registration link] // or confirm by answering this email.

Thank you for your attention. We hope this initiative will be of interest to you.

Kind regards

Mail to be sent after the event

Once the event was finished, an email needed to be sent to attendees including all the materials used during the event and the satisfaction survey (if not shared before). An example of this email is provided below:

Dear ROBIN regional event attendee

Thank you so much for join us during the ROBIN regional event. Enclosed/Here[hyperlink] you can find the materials used during the event. Also, please feel free to check the project website in order to be regularly updated about ROBIN project progress and results <https://robin-project.eu/>.

It would be nice if you could answer the following satisfaction survey and provide your feedback about the event. It would not take you more than five minutes! This information is very important for us in order to improve upcoming activities and to offer you the most relevant event contents and formats.

Best regards,

....

2.8 Satisfaction survey

Once the event was finished, hosts would gather feedback from the attendees in order to assess the success of the action and to learn about attendees' expectations, potential overlooks that might have occurred or tentative improvements that can be considered in further events.

An example of the satisfaction survey template prepared can be found in Annex 5. This could have been done either online (link sent by email to attendees, implemented in MS Forms, Google Forms or any other platform) or by providing hard copies as part of the participant package. It was recommended that, for face-to-face events, the satisfaction survey was sent by e-mail to attendees that did not complete it on hard copy at the end of the event.

3. Regional events organization

Main results and outcomes of the regional events organized following the previous guidelines are provided next.

Andalusia regional event

Andalusian regional event organization

Official event title

The event was named “Taller de co-creación- Región de Andalucía. Proyecto ROBIN”

Regional customisation

The event was held in Spanish to facilitate the participation of people and the discussion.

CTA carried out the preparation of the workshop in collaboration with the other regional ROBIN partners: CAP and IFA.

Figure 4. Save-the-date for the Andalusian regional event

The attendees were selected from the regional ROBIN MARC list, enlarged with other relevant regional stakeholders, but always keeping a limited number of participants to allow a smooth discussion dynamic with enough time for all to participate.

The attendees were initially contacted by phone by the closest regional partner in order to personally inform them about the event and invite them. For those who confirmed, an invitation by email was sent to them, with a dedicated link for the registration¹.

Once the registration was received, 1-2 days before the event celebration, another email was sent thanking them for their participation and asking them to fill in the *baseline monitoring survey*, in order to have a little more information to focus on the event.

Below is the email sent translated from Spanish:

Hello!

Thank you for your participation in the Co-Creation Workshop of the European ROBIN project to boost the Circular Bioeconomy in the Andalusia region.

We need you to fill in the following questionnaire (5 min) to guide the event and make it as interesting and effective as possible.

[*Answer the questionnaire here.*](#)

Thank you! See you tomorrow. Best regards,

The regional ROBIN partners decided to prepare the event by pre-filling the regional SWOT analysis and the CBGMC, including a physical paper in the participant package. In addition, the CBGMC was printed in poster size (A1) to be displayed in the room during the whole workshop (Figure 5. CANVAS in poster size

Figure 5. CANVAS in poster size

¹ In-person event 04/05 Co-creation Workshop Andalucía ROBIN project (campaign-archive.com)

Agenda

The agenda of the event translated from Spanish is provided below:

11:00-11:30 Introduction

- Attendees welcome
- Round of introductions
- ROBIN project presentation and Andalusia overview

11:30-11:50 Session 1 - Regional analysis

- Presentation and discussion about regional SWOT analysis

11:50-13:30 Session 2 - Governance action design

- Prioritisation of actions at regional level
- Interactive discussion to define the regional CANVAS

13:30-14:30 Cocktail-Networking

Figure 6. Original agenda

Date, host, registration and venue

Date: May 4, 2023

Host: CAP, IFA and CTA

Registration: The registration was done via CTA website:

[Evento presencial 04/05 Cocreation Workshop Andalucía ROBIN project \(campaign-archive.com\)](https://campaign-archive.com/evento-presencial-04/05-cocreation-workshop-andalucia-robin-project)

Venue: Face-to-face. EOI headquarters (PCT Cartuja, Sevilla), Figure 7.

Figure 7. Picture of the event venue

Required equipment, material, logistics

We offered a warm welcome to the attendees with a coffee catering service that was available throughout the event.

A physical “participant folder” was provided to each attendee, including the following documents:

- ROBIN and CTA information flyers.
- The Regional Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework scheme.
- The initial regional SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) pre-filled.
- The pre-filled regional CANVAS scheme and a guidelines document with information about the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas (CBGMC) tool guidelines, as well as further explanation of the content included in the scheme.
- The event agenda, note-taking paper, and a pen.
- The baseline monitoring survey.
- The event satisfaction survey.

Registration was done via the CTA website. MARC members were personally invited to the event, along with other stakeholders who joined the MARC after the event.

The online monitoring baseline survey was conducted using the Google Forms platform. The link was sent via email before the event.

For the regional SWOT analysis and regional CBGMC, pre-filled templates were created and used during the event.

The online tool Mentimeter was used for the prioritisation of actions at a regional level, linked to the information included in the Governance Model Co-creation Framework.

The satisfaction survey was collected from the participants at the end of the event as a hard copy. A signature sheet was also prepared and circulated among participants during the event.

At the end of the event, a standing cocktail was offered to the attendees which facilitated networking actions.

Finally, after the event, all presentations were sent to attendees, along with the main results obtained from the workshop.

Participants

A total of 16 participants (Figure 8) took part in the event. The invitation was sent to MARCs members as well as to other stakeholders who have joined MARCs since the event: Figure 8

2 policy makers, 4 researchers and academics, 2 civil society representatives, 6 business and SME representatives and 2 Others.

Figure 8. Workshop participants

Results from introductory session (project presentation + baseline monitoring survey)

The day began with a welcome from a representative of each of the regional entities participating in the project: Mar Cátedra (CAP), Carmen Capote (CAP), Samir Sayadi (IFA) and María García (CTA) (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Welcome from the organisers to the participants.

Mar Cátedra opened the workshop by giving an overview of the ROBIN project using the template provided by White Research.

As mentioned earlier, the baseline monitoring survey was primarily conducted using the Google Forms platform (through the link sent to the invitees via email prior to the event). Additionally, a few responses (2) were collected physically during the event. In total, 16 responses were received.

The results of the survey are shown below (Figure 10):

Figure 10. Andalusia Baseline presentation

Results from session 1 (regional analysis: background, potential of biomass and SWOT analysis)

Mar Cátedra (CAP) proceeded with the regional analysis, presenting the primary biomass resources of Andalusia, which mainly include agriculture (olive trees and horticulture) and livestock (pig and bovine) (Figure 11). She concluded her presentation by explaining to the audience the main objectives of the workshop. There were no additional questions from the attendees.

Figure 11. Andalusia potential of biomass presentation

Figure 12. Andalusia SWOT presentation

After that, Samir Sayadi (IFA) presented the prefilled Andalusia SWOT analysis (Figure 12). He used a PowerPoint presentation and went through all the points included in each section: strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Attendees had the opportunity to ask questions and share their points of view. Some modifications were made to the initial pre-filled SWOT version and included in the final analysis.

Results from session 2 (Governance action design)

The workshop continued with the participation of Carmen Capote (CAP), who used a PowerPoint presentation to introduce the Regional Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework (RCBGMF) to the attendees (Figure 13).

She provided an explanation of the tool and requested the collaboration of the attendees to prioritise the areas using the Mentimeter tool (<https://www.mentimeter.com/app/presentation/alvhwig5y2h5um1m2yz215k86cdoo4n3/porksy1k7fts/edit>).

Regarding the RCBGMF, some participants expressed that it seemed odd to have certain areas linked to actions while others were associated with impacts. They suggested renaming the “impacts” to align them with the others.

Figure 13. Regional Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework presentation

Finally, María García (CTA) introduced the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas to the participants. The pre-filled model was presented using the Miro platform (<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMMo37zM=/>) allowing to directly add comments of the participants (using online post-its) on the canvas (Figure 14). She explained each section of the canvas pointing out the information initially included. The attendees had the opportunity to express their opinion and some modifications were made to the initial model.

Figure 14. Andalusia Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model CANVAS pre-filled

Satisfaction survey results

As mentioned earlier, the satisfaction survey was included as a hard copy in the material provided within the participant folder (Annex 1). A graph showing the main results is shown below (Figure 15):

Figure 15. Satisfaction survey results

As general comments, some participants indicated the following:

- Excellent organisation, very interesting structure and content, very adequate and tight time and, above all, very good interaction and dynamics.

- A task chart would be nice. Congratulations.
- Consider online meetings option for future ROBIN MARC meetings.
- The session went well. It would be good to have the content in advance of the event in order to be able to reflect on it.
- It is still difficult to assess the suitability of the tools. More advanced tools may be needed for the planning stages.

Andalusian regional governance model

The context

Andalusia is located in the Southwest of Europe with an extension of more than 87.000 km² (ca. 9Mha) and 940 km of coastline. From that, the agricultural area covers 4,4 Mha and the forest area covers 4,6Mha. Andalusia is the most populated area in Spain, with around 8.400,000 inhabitants. Andalusia has historically been an agricultural region, compared to the rest of Spain and the rest of Europe. The primary sector constitutes an important source of employment due to the link among people and the environment since 51% of the population lives in rural areas where resources are mainly being produced¹.

Agriculture biomass production reaches more than 8 million tons a year, highlighting sectors such as olive groves (29%), horticulture (18%), wheat straw (13%) and corn straw (5%). There is also the availability of other interesting waste streams such as paper & pulp, sewage sludge, plastics and MSW (municipal solid waste)².

The biomass potential identified in Andalusia amounts to 3,955 ktoe (Kilotons of oil equivalent) of which 1,322 ktoe are agricultural waste, 77 ktoe are livestock waste, 1,023 ktoe correspond to industrial waste, 322 ktoe are forest biomass, 620 ktoe are from energy crops and 591 ktoe are urban waste³.

At the regional level, the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy (ACBS) was developed by the former Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development (CAPADR by its name in Spanish) and approved by the Andalusian Government on September 18th, 2018. The strategy focuses on the regional bioeconomy areas less developed and aims to support the implementation of specific actions that facilitate its take-off and consolidation in the medium-long term. The relevant sectors for the bioeconomy include agriculture and agro-industries, livestock, forestry, fishing, aquaculture, seaweed production, food and paper production, as well as part of the chemical, biotechnology and energy industries.

¹<https://online.1stflip.com/dxnb/3lug/>

²<https://online.1stflip.com/dxnb/3lug/>

³ PNO, CEFIC, CIRCE. (2016). *Andalusia as a model demonstrator*.

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High production capacity of biomass resources derived from agriculture, livestock, agro-industry, forestry, and fishing, as well as sewage sludge and municipal bio-waste. - Important agro-industrial fabric with the capacity to participate in bio-based processes, continuous development of bioenergy and a favourable biotechnological ecosystem for the transformation and valorisation of biological resources. - Growing demand from the sector for traditional uses of certain bioproducts: plant waste for composting, manure for organic fertilisers. - Existence of successful and consolidated good practices in circular bioeconomy that can be applied on a larger scale. - Knowledge, experience, human capital, and technological capacity in innovation areas, sectors and companies related to the circular bioeconomy. - Existence of cross-cutting policies that promote and support the circular bioeconomy. - Potential synergies between sectors and actors involved in the region. - Development of regulatory and planning instruments related to aspects linked to the circular bioeconomy, as well as political commitment in all areas to the bioeconomy, the circular economy and sustainability. - Increasing awareness of sustainable food. - Growing social demand for sustainable products and value attributes based on the circular bioeconomy in the agri-food value chain. - Increasing the number of profiles related to the bioeconomy, which facilitates the implementation and structuring of the model. - The agri-food value chain in Andalusia is very well structured. - The academic sector in Andalusia is very well organised, as there is an adequate network of scientific-technological infrastructures in the region. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Territorial and temporal seasonality of biomass resources, as well as diversity. - Lack of optimised logistics centres for good management of biomass resources along the value chain. - Scarce development of integrated biorefineries and bio-based industries. - Difficulties in moving from prototyping to commercial scale-up of bio-based products. - Lack of standardisation of these new bioproducts concerning other more innovative ones already established. - Deficient business culture of innovation to face the technological adaptation of new products and manufacturing processes. - Lack of specific, clear, and recognised regulation for products of biological origin. - Lack of social awareness of what the circular bioeconomy means and implies, as well as deficient promotion of products and services derived from activities associated with the circular bioeconomy. - Lack of joint initiatives between the R&D&I system and the associated sectors, and lack of knowledge of the sector's demands in terms of the circular bioeconomy. - Insufficiently flexible financing instruments for technology-based companies. - Lack of facilitating mechanisms for the establishment of alliances between stakeholders in the quadruple helix.

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulatory changes in European, national, and regional legislation that favour, encourage, and even oblige the reuse of by-products from the production chain. - Possibility of improving and computerising logistical operations through the use of ICT technologies. - Development of small-scale bio-industries and bio-refineries in rural areas of Andalusia (olive groves, fruit, vegetables, etc.). - Possibility of integrating waste managers as logistics centres in the recovery chain. - Growing interest and demand from industry in the use of resources of biological origin and by-products of the circular bioeconomy. - Potential for the development of business models and market opportunities based on these new products and attributes. - Growing interest in sustainable investment. - Dimension and technological development of the Andalusian public sector that allows it to act as an incentive for demand, innovative public procurement, and business driver. - Taking advantage of the "innovation broker" profile, which is fundamental for integrating the AKIS (Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems) into this model. - Cooperation approach under the quadruple helix model represents a social opportunity. - Possibility of presenting the bioeconomy to Andalusian society as a standard of knowledge and included within the business culture. - Potential to take advantage of existing legislation to be able to catalogue these bioproducts and not just focus on new waste regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decrease in the amount of biomass resources available due to the effects of climate change. - Deficiencies in the connection between Andalusian regional centres and other international markets. - High costs of new technologies for companies and low market availability. - Uncertainty in the development of possible markets and the existence of competition with cheaper non-renewable products. - Low production yields of bioproducts and high costs associated with them. - Lack of clarity in the transmission of the concept of the circular bioeconomy and lack of adequate communication and dissemination channels that hinder its understanding and adoption among the different agents involved. - Relative disconnection between the business structure and the Andalusian knowledge system, and reduced activity of many components of the latter, which reduces the potential for improvement and development of the most innovative industry. - Difficulty of access and limited capacity for private sector financing, especially for SMEs. - Difficulty, administrative obstacles and complexity for the implementation and development of innovative circular bioeconomy projects in the territory.

Identification of the regional Governance Model improvement areas

1) Identified and prioritised actions from the Governance Model Co-Creation Framework

The result of the prioritisation of actions was as follows:

- Reduce dependence on non-renewable resources.
- Strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs.
- Managing natural resources sustainably.
- Ensuring food and nutrition security.
- Mitigating and adapting to climate change.
- Environmental benefits.
- Social benefits.
- Regional benefits.

Below is an image of the result obtained in the Mentimeter tool (Figure 1616):

Figure 16. Prioritisation of the strategic areas of the RCBMF for Andalusia

2) Selected improvement area as main goal to achieve within the ROBIN project at regional level.

Strengthening regional tools and plans for the promotion and dissemination of the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia by consolidating the sector through the creation of a regional circular bioeconomy node.

Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Results

REGIONAL VISION/VALUE PROPOSITION

Strengthening regional tools and plans for the promotion and dissemination of the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia.

Consolidation of the sector through the creation of a regional circular bioeconomy node that:

- Organises regional actors from the quadruple helix,
- Supports the creation of regional strategies and legislation,
- Stimulates investment in unique and strategic infrastructure,
- Promotes entrepreneurship, knowledge of the sector and market trends adaptation,

- Serves as a regional observatory of the bioeconomy,
- Coordinates regional capacities, and
- Seeks opportunities and advocates for regional interests in national and European forums.

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

- Enhancing the regional deployment of the bioeconomy and its positive environmental impact on the region.
- Promoting the sustainable use of all biomass resources in the region through the opportunities they provide.
- Reducing regional dependence on non-renewable and unsustainable resources.
- Contributing to climate change mitigation and adaptation.
- Fostering environmental and territorial sustainability in sectors and regions (environmental sustainability).

ECONOMIC BENEFITS

- The emergence of new economic activities and value chains.
- Diversification of economic activities in rural territories (economic sustainability).
- Increased market opportunities and development of new bio-products and new business models.
- Increased competitiveness and added value based on quality attributes of circular bioeconomy (profitability).
- Promoting the access of node members to public funds (national or international).
- Connecting the financial sector with the private and academic-scientific sectors.
- Promotion of technological knowledge and sustainable practices of handling and management of resources, waste and by-products.
- Job creation and associated economic growth.

SOCIAL BENEFITS

- Strengthening the recognition and collaboration of regional stakeholders.
- Promotion of open innovation actions among members is important to connect science with business and accelerate development.
- Communication and dissemination of the positive externalities that the circular bioeconomy brings to the region.
- Creation of direct and indirect employment in the bioeconomy sector (local labour).
- Meeting new demands and promoting the consumption of bioproducts.
- Contribution to sustainable development and social welfare (social sustainability).
- Ensuring food security.
- Reduction of territorial inequalities.

ACTIVITIES

1. Update of the regional situation diagnosis.
2. Prospective analysis of relevant actors.
3. Involvement of key stakeholders and strategic members of the quadruple helix.
4. Alignment with regional strategies.
5. Development of a 3-5 year strategic plan.
6. Identification of resources needed for the creation and implementation of the node.
7. Development of a multi-annual action plan.

8. Study of the annualised budget, identification of possible sources of funds and analysis of financing opportunities.
9. Development of a 3-5 year economic-financial viability model for the node, based on the established strategic plan.
10. Development of a communication plan for the node, including its mission, vision and a work plan to improve its image, positioning, and visibility.
11. Campaign to raise awareness and attract members.
12. Analysis of the best legal instrument for the constitution of the node (agreements, statutes).
13. Establishment of the node and its organisational structure.

PARTNERSHIPS

- Public Administration.
- First members.
- European, regional and national bioeconomy clusters or platforms.
- Specialised external entities for advice, funding, etc.

RESOURCES

- Staff.
- Facilities.
- Technical resources (IT).
- Financing.

INFRASTRUCTURES

Not applicable

REGIONAL ACTORS/STAKEHOLDERS

Quadruple helix:

- Public sector.
- Academic and scientific sector.
- Private sector.
- Civil society.

REGIONAL RELATIONSHIPS

- Node's communication committee.
- Development of a communication plan and brand identity.
- Networking with other national and European clusters.

CHANNELS

- Dedicated website and social networks.
- Node's own promotional events.
- Bioeconomy events and other sectoral and disciplinary events of third parties.

REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT REQUIREMENTS

- Personnel and resources.
- Guarantee of support for the technical and economic feasibility plan.

REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT POLICY/OUTCOMES

- Alignment with global bioeconomy strategies (European, Central America, North Africa) and with the region's strategic policies.
- Alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
- Strengthening the sector in the region.
- Positioning of Andalusia as a bioregion.
- Developing and updating of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy (EABC).

The final result of the Andalusia CBGMC is shown in Figure 1717:

Figure 17. Andalusia Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model CANVAS

Baden-Württemberg regional event

Baden-Württemberg regional event organization

Official event title

The official title of the event was “ROBIN Projekt – Workshop zu Bioökonomie in Baden-Württemberg”.

Regional customisation

The event was held in German language. The agenda was slightly adapted: the first session did not consist of a SWOT Analysis *per se*; it was an activity based on parts of a business model canvas, particularly in the parts “Jobs”, “Pains” and “Value proposition”. The output of the first session should be the selection of 3 value propositions -more than one, as agreed with the regional authority on beforehand- to be shaped in the second session. The latter was dedicated to fill-in the governance model canvas. The 10 participants were divided in three groups (3-4 participants) to work respectively with each of the value propositions selected in the first session.

Agenda

Time	Topic
09:30 - 09:45	Welcome, Main objectives of the workshop & Tour de Table
09:45 - 10:00	ROBIN Project presentation
10:00 - 11:10	Session I: Value Propositions and Improvement aspects in the implementation of the Bioeconomy in Baden-Württemberg
11:10 - 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 - 12:40	Session II: Identification of support actions in view of further strategic developments in Baden-Württemberg and Europe
12:40 - 13:00	Evaluation Survey, Conclusions and Next Steps
From 13:00	Networking lunch

Date, host, registration and venue

Date: 02/05/2023

Host: S2I, BPRO

Registration: via e-mail (personal invitation)

Venue: Steinbeis Europa Zentrum - Leuschnerstr. 43, 70176 Stuttgart, Germany (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Picture of the session in Stuttgart, Germany

Required equipment, material, logistics

The following equipment and material were used for the event:

- 1 Laptop
- 1 Monitor
- 3 posters of the canvas (A0 size)
- 3 Pinboards
- 1 Moderation case (stickers, markers, sticky notes)
- 1 Room of ca. 60-70 m²

Participants

Twelve participants registered to the Workshop. From them, four were from the industry/business area, one policy maker, four research organisations, one independent consultant and one regional development agency. Additionally, from the organisation side (project partners) the following persons attended:

- Sergi Costa (BIOPRO Baden-Württemberg)
- Alejandra Campos (S2i)
- Jennifer Bilbao (S2i)
- Lucia Hörner (S2i)

Results from introductory session (project presentation + baseline monitoring survey)

The first 30 minutes were dedicated to introducing the aim of the workshop, to give a brief presentation of each attendee and an overview of the ROBIN project. The baseline monitoring survey was circulated with the official agenda on beforehand (email) and responded by 11 participants.

The results of the survey are shown below:

1. Current type of involvement in the regional bioeconomy sector

2. Time working in the current position

3. Understanding of the bioeconomy concept

4. Level of development of bioeconomy in the region

5.1 Designing of bioeconomy governance models and practices

5.2 Implementation of governance models and practices

5.3 Monitoring and evaluation of governance models and practices

6. Effectiveness of the bioeconomy governance model in achieving regional development goals

Figure 19. Baden-Württemberg baseline presentation

Results from session 1 (regional analysis: background, potential of biomass and SWOT analysis)

The first session was inspired on some categories of a standard business model canvas; it followed the next steps:

- Asking the participants about the categories “Jobs” (which are the activities that the participant carry out in the bioeconomy area), “Pains” (which are the difficulties or hurdles that they have in order to fulfil their jobs) and their “value propositions” (what would help them to aminorate their pains). See Figure 20 and Table 2.
- A canvas in size DIN A0 (Figure 20) was used to collect feedback of the 10 participants using sticky notes that were located in the respective canvas categories accordingly.
- 4 value propositions resulted from the exercise: “Policy framework”, “Funding/Financing”, “Communication”, and “Matchmaking and partner search.”
- Before the coffee break the participants had the opportunity to rate the results and select their preferences. Each of them was given 3 points to distribute among the options: 1) **Policy framework** (12 points); 2) **Matchmaking and partner search** (9 points); 3) **Funding/Financing** (7 points); and 4) **Communication** (1 point). See Figure 21.

Figure 20. Empty CANVAS used in the first session (in which "Aufgaben" means Jobs and "Schmerzen" means Pains)

Figure 21. CANVAS resulting from the first session (in orange are "Jobs", in blue "Pains" and in green "Value propositions")

Table 2. Translation of the most important contributions to the CANVAS of the first session

Jobs	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of bioeconomic solutions with the most synergies • Being a contact person and matchmaker • Matching ideas with suitable funding • Strengthen (regional) cooperation • Bring together people from different fields (also from society) • Making biopolymers marketable • Bringing social innovation into technically driven projects • Keeping value creation in the region • Monitor competition from abroad • Set up funding programmes with a timeframe of minimum 3 years
Pains	
<i>Cooperation partners:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find the right contact persons • Identify and contact suitable/appropriate cooperation partners • Establish contact with and involve different groups in society
<i>Communication:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange only takes place among people who are already involved in the bioeconomy anyway • Interdisciplinary exchange requires knowledge in different areas • Bioeconomy is not present in the general public as a concept • Lack of tangible examples of the bioeconomy to make it understandable for companies/public (along the value chain) • Lack of good examples that provide arguments for the continuation of funding programmes

Scalability:

- Bioeconomy sometimes only works on a large scale ; starting/testing on a small scale is not sufficient for meaningful results
- New business formats are necessary
- Bioeconomy is also part of the global economic system. Don't forget to think about the global market dimension!

Framework conditions:

- Heterogeneity of the bioeconomy: How to bring together raw materials, actors and markets?
- Restriction and constraints inhibiting innovation
- Divergence between regionality & internationality

Customers:

- Who is the right customer for my product?
- Lack of willingness among customers to pay more for "sustainability"

Financial resources:

- Few proposals submitted with a high TRL
- Identify suitable funding
- Lack of/limited financial resources
- Missing financial resources for transition between start-up and SME
- Find suitable co-financing; often only available temporarily
- No one wants to be "first" in funding as risk is too high
- Banks do not have the experience to be allowed to finance innovation in the bioeconomy
- Funding conditions. Advance payment necessary/helpful for liquidity
- Venture Capital wants to finance products and not the technology/system behind them
- EU funding: sometimes too slow, you get overtaken if you wait for EIC (European Innovation Council) grants
- More public funding available for Research & Innovation than for implementation

Value propositions

Funding/Financing:

- Evaluation system for bioeconomy innovations (economic viability assessment) for financial decisions
- Matching co-financing with year-round application phase
- Funding that does not run according to the typical project funding framework (not just 3-5 years); one often does not know on beforehand; more flexible research funding
- Simple risk coverage

Matchmaking/partner search:

- Use of AI for matchmaking among partners from different backgrounds
- Bioeconomy cluster with various players in Baden-Württemberg / networking of platforms (entire value chain)

Communication:

- Make visible what already exists
- Integrate the bioeconomy into the education curriculum Raise awareness at an early stage

Framework conditions:

- Framework conditions that help companies to grow
- Create incentives so that existing companies also engage with the bioeconomy
- State government must know the goals to be able to address them
- Instruments that make the results of research scalable (e.g., indemnity, guarantee)
- Strategic Hot Topics
- Streamlining/unification of policy measures (regional/national/EU)
- LCA for bioeconomy products and participation in emissions trading
- Bringing climate protection and bioeconomy together (also in terms of communication)
- "Bioeconomy readiness level" with Use Cases

Results from session 2

The second session was based on the governance model canvas developed in WP2 (T2.3). The canvas was printed in A0 size, and 3 copies were distributed in 3 pinboards for each of the selected value propositions (Policy Framework, Matchmaking and partner search, and Funding/Financing). The aim of the session was to fill-in the 3 CANVAS with the contributions of the participants; they were distributed in 3 groups (4 participants for the first value proposition and 3 participants for the second and third value propositions, respectively). The duration for completion of each canvas was 70 minutes.

3 project representatives moderated the discussions respectively. In the first value proposition (**policy framework**) there was a preliminary discussion with the participants in order to decide on which sub-themes to focus. It was aimed at limiting the scope of the activity, so the exercise could be manageable within the timeframe set.

The order of the sections while filling-in the canvas was different to the one suggested by the Task leader (MTU). It resulted as follows: 1) Value proposition; 1a) Environmental benefits; 1b) Economic benefits; 1c) Social benefits; 2) Regional actors/Stakeholders; 3) Regional relationships; 4) Channels; 5) Activities; 6) Partnerships; 7) Resources; 8) Infrastructure; 9) Regional development requirements; 10) Regional development policy/outcomes.

The moderator was responsible to collect, synthesise and write the inputs from the participants, as well as filling-in the canvas.

The piloting of the canvas drew some suggestions for potential improvements, some of them collected through the evaluation survey, others from own elaboration:

- 5 participants would be the maximum number of participants recommended to work with the canvas if the session's duration is set to 60-70 minutes
- The size of the canvas might be an issue e.g. size A0 may result too small; one can have different approaches depending on how the information is collected or synthesised (see Figures 22 and 23)
- Some participants informed that some of the categories are a bit unclear or somehow repetitive, particularly related with "regional actors/stakeholders", "partnerships" and / or "regional relationships". One participant found similarities between "Activities" and "Channels". According to this person, it might be helpful to reduce the number of fields to the essential ones.
- One of the participants mentioned that the value proposition "Policy Framework" was a too vast topic to be worked with the canvas.

Figure 22. Part of the governance model CANVAS (2nd value proposition: Matchmaking and partner search)

Figure 23. Governance model CANVAS (1st value proposition: Policy framework)

Satisfaction survey results

8 out of 10 participants responded to the online evaluation survey that was distributed short before the end of the event. In general, the workshop was (very) well valued. The marks were mainly positive (4) or very positive (5) in the categories “Organisation”, “Relevance of the topic”, “Quality and clarity of the presentation and workshop” and “Interaction and dialogue between participants” (which obtained the best mark); the category of “Usefulness of the Regional Governance Canvas” was the most disagreeing with marks ranging from 1 to 5 depending on the participant.

Baden-Württemberg regional governance model

The context

The bioeconomy in Baden-Württemberg is developed since 2013, firstly with a Bioeconomy Research Programme that funded research projects on this topic. A SWOT exercise done in 2013 was based in three pillars: i) raw materials from supply side (agri-, wood-based, aquatic, bio-waste and by-products); ii) products and valorisation from demand side (food use, material use, energetic use); and iii) cross-cutting areas covering ecological, societal, ethical and economic aspects.

Later, a regional strategy for sustainable bioeconomy was launched in June 2019. The strategy is based on the Bioeconomy Research Programme and aims at scaling up the results of this programme. After nearly five years of implementation, the leading Ministries are currently working in an update of the strategy, expected to be completed in the first part of 2024. The ongoing implementation of the strategy has already/will bring effects at all levels: economic, social and environmental.

The most relevant biomass feedstocks of Baden Württemberg are wood, lignin, lignocellulose, bio-waste, agricultural production and by-products (e.g. from harvest or digestates) and insects.

The activity of Session 1 was not based on a SWOT analysis. During that session some “Jobs” and “Pains” of the participants were outlined. The “Pains” are linked with the “Job” undertaken, which at the same time strive to the consecution of the related “value proposition”. According to Table 2, the “Jobs” identified are the following:

- Identification of bioeconomic solutions with the most synergies
- Being a contact person and matchmaker
- Matching ideas with suitable funding
- Strengthen cooperation (regional) cooperation
- Bring together people from different fields (also from society)
- Making biopolymers marketable
- Bringing social innovation into technically driven projects
- Keeping value creation in the region
- Monitor competition from abroad

Some **key barriers** and/or **challenges** in the implementation of the bioeconomy in Baden-Württemberg were identified in the discussions of the first session. They are mainly identified in the figure below in which some categories were merged for the purpose of concision:

Table 3. Main key barriers and/or challenges identified in the first session

Policy framework <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Appropriate scope of the framework: regionality vs internationality• Heterogeneity of the bioeconomy• Regulation vs Innovation	Building cooperation <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Difficulty to engage different societal groups, thus achieving a quadruple / penta helix approach• Finding the suitable contact person
Funding/Financing <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Appropriate co-funding sources, including level of funding amount	Customers <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Willingness-to-pay for “sustainable” products / services

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different paces between funding acquisition and market needs • Banking & investors not having enough knowledge of the bioeconomy • Financial support of the transition from start-up to SME • Scalability and associated risks: difficulty to start and test bioeconomic innovations at the small scale 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of the suitable customer
<p>Communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of the bioeconomy by the layman • Cross-sectoral nature of the bioeconomy that requires interdisciplinary knowledge. • Lack of comprehensive examples of bioeconomy that can be traced through the value chain and be understood by the industry 	

Identification of the regional Governance Model improvement areas

Based on the results of the Governance Model Canvas, the representatives of the regional node and the supporting Ministry identified the following **support actions to be considered as recommendations** within the current policy process in the region:

1. Further development of the bioeconomy strategy in Baden-Württemberg through a Bioeconomy Strategy 2.0 that should be in place by the end of 2024
2. Further development of funding instruments to support industrialisation (e.g., risk capital credit, sector-specific funding)
3. Creation of more matchmaking opportunities between stakeholders related to collaboration in public funded projects
4. New funding instruments for scaling-up
5. Define target groups
6. Further development of life cycle assessment/environmental footprint assessment via funding instruments
7. Set an evaluation system for bioeconomy innovations (e.g., economic viability assessment) for financial decisions
8. Match co-financing with year-round application phase

The regional authority in Baden-Württemberg that is supporting the ROBIN Project, the Ministry of Food, Rural Affairs and Consumer Protection confirmed that the suggested support actions developed in ROBIN project will be considered as recommendation/s for policy purposes. The update of the regional bioeconomy strategy is currently under development and shall be finalized in 2024.

During the workshop discussions it was mentioned several times the need to adapt some of the funding instruments to the needs of some enterprises e.g., helping the transition from start-up to SME, or supporting more the associated risks related to scaling-up bioeconomic innovations. The fact that some banks or investors do not own enough knowledge of the bioeconomy was indicated as another improvement area. The resulting regional vision strives for positioning companies in Baden-Württemberg as world market leaders in the bioeconomy sector, with a special focus on small and medium-sized enterprises. Toward this vision and the eight listed support actions above, an

action plan will be developed in Task 2.2 and should/could be implemented through WP3 or before project's end, as far as the needed resources are allocated.

Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Results

The main results from the piloting exercise of the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas related to the value proposition "Funding / Financing" are presented below.

1) **Regional vision/value proposition:** As mentioned in the previous section, the regional vision is that **companies in Baden-Württemberg, especially small and medium-sized, become world market leaders in the bioeconomy sector and that more innovative bioeconomic ideas are developed.** For this, it is necessary to further develop suitable funding support schemes.

The advantages that are expected by the financial support and development of bioeconomy in the region are environmental (i.e., reduction in the emission of greenhouse gases), economic (i.e., security of raw material supply and autonomy of the region and future prosperity) and social (i.e. secure jobs and well-being).

2) **Regional actors:** The main regional actors from supply and demand side are politicians/policy-makers, investors, companies, universities/research institutions and other active multipliers of the bioeconomy in the region.

3) **Regional relationships:** The development of relationships with all the stakeholders is crucial. Within the work filling-out the canvas, it was stressed that clusters are important to maintain the relationship among stakeholders. They can be focused on specific sectors and at several region levels (e.g., provincial, state) too. Due to the interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral nature of the bioeconomy, their role of pooling competences and informing on bioeconomy is undeniable. On the other hand, promoting regional matchmaking events related to funding programmes could be a good idea to interlink interests and organisations. Moreover, the ongoing "Thematic Initiatives" (*Fachinitiativen*), one of the measures funded through the regional bioeconomy strategy, are a good example of connecting different actors of the quadruple helix; the identification and participation in public funded projects can be an opportunity coming from those networks.

4) **Channels:** The best channels to address the actors is direct contact by e.g., regional networking events. Also, to offer comprehensive databases with information, which could also be supported by AI tools.

5) **Activities:** Eight support activities were chosen and can be considered as basis for the action plan to support the delivery of the value proposition.

1. Further development of the bioeconomy strategy in Baden-Württemberg through a Bioeconomy Strategy 2.0 that should be in place by the end of 2024
2. Further development of funding instruments to support industrialisation (e.g., risk capital credit, sector-specific funding)
3. Creation of more matchmaking opportunities between stakeholders related to collaboration in public funded projects
4. New funding instruments for scaling-up
5. Define target groups
6. Further development of life cycle assessment/environmental footprint assessment via funding instruments
7. Set an evaluation system for bioeconomy innovations (e.g., economic viability assessment) for financial decisions
8. Match co-financing with year-round application phase

6) **Partnerships:** Partnerships between the state and their financing organisations (e.g. LBBW, BW-Bank, L-Bank) are important so more companies can obtain support. Moreover, it is important to promote a cluster between small business (Start-ups, SMEs)

7) **Resources:** Knowledgeable investors and public bank officers, skilled workers and experts in bioeconomy technologies are important resources. Also venture capital financing can contribute to support the bioeconomy-related innovation aspirations of companies.

8) **Infrastructure:** It is necessary to provide special advisory services and consulting regarding financing for bioeconomy. Additionally, the state could be more active in the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) to promote investments in low-carbon technologies.

9) **Effort at regional level:** The main effort for the state is to provide the resources needed and minimize bureaucracy to encourage more bioeconomy-related ventures.

10) **Regional added value:** The added value for the region is that the investments made via financing for bioeconomy innovation will be returned as economic, environmental and social benefits.

Central Macedonia regional event

Central Macedonia regional event organization

Official event title

Title: ROBIN Region of Central Macedonia Co-Creation Workshop

Figure 24. Official invitation of ROBIN Region of Central Macedonia Co-creation Workshop

Regional customisation

The event was conducted in Greek, based on the guidelines provided by Task leader CTA. The regional partners (QPL and RCM) firstly introduced the ROBIN project, followed by a discussion on the Regional Analysis (AUTH). This change ensured that attendees had an overview of the current stat of play in the Region of Central Macedonia before answering the survey, which would result in more accurate baseline survey results. A coffee break relatively early in the agenda allowed the participants to network, exchange information on the region, and ultimately contribute with more precise baseline survey answers. Indeed, after the coffee break, the baseline monitoring survey was implemented, after which the team conducted a warm-up exercise on biomass feedstocks, followed by the presentation of the co-creation framework and the process for filling in the canvas. The exercise effectively facilitated the group's transition into Session 2 of the co-creation workshop by directing their attention to relevant subjects within the bioeconomy spectrum. The co-creation framework was presented using an A0 printed sheet, a decision made to enhance dynamism within the context and provide initial information to familiarize participants with the subsequent hands-on canvas section. The participants were divided across three co-creation tables, with participants of each table co-creating their own canvas. After the completion of the co-creation exercise, the team distributed the feedback survey on paper for response collection, resulting in a significantly faster data collection process.

Agenda

Regional Co-Creation Workshop

Thursday, June 8, 2023

TEF - Stand 15 (Ground Floor | Stand:C07)

Time	
10.00 – 10.10	Welcome and Introduction A brief presentation of the European project ROBIN and the main objectives of the workshop – Region of Central Macedonia & QPLAN International
10.10 – 10.25	Bioeconomy – Regional Context Presentation of the regional bioeconomy context, regional governance model and SWOT analysis – Region of Central Macedonia
10.25 – 10.45	Interactive Workshop – 1 Regional Framework Participants share their view on the regional framework – QPLAN International
10.45 – 11.00	Coffee Break
11.00 – 11.15	Interactive Workshop – 2 Definition of Improvement Areas Prioritization of the support actions for the transition to the bioeconomy – Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
11.15 – 11.50	Interactive Workshop – 3 Draft of the Governance Model Co-creation of the circular bioeconomy governance model canvas – Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
11.50 – 12.00	Summary - Conclusions ROBIN next steps, action planned at regional level and satisfaction survey – QPLAN International
12.00 – 13.00	Meeting of the Regional Support Group of the project “CITISYSTEM” - Supporting cities in sustainable biobased systemic change” – Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia

Figure 25. Central Macedonia agenda

See Annex 6 for the original agenda in local language.

Date, host, registration and venue

Date: 08/06/2023

Host: Region of Central Macedonia, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Q-PLAN International

Registration: via Google Form

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfdVidN2t74X2PTVZTKdbScu1Z5hLMZeDBOAxUKPAseIA_knQ/closedform

Venue: 1st International Exhibition on the Circular Economy, Forward Green (FG Expo)

Figure 26. Some of the workshop attendees at the closing of the event

Required equipment, material, logistics

In preparation for the event, the partners arranged for the printing of 4 blank A0 canvases (out of which only 3 were eventually used) of the ROBIN circular bioeconomy governance models, along with 1 A0 sheet for the prioritization of support actions. Leaflets featuring ROBIN information, participant name tags with the ROBIN logo, and spare tags were also printed. Necessary stationery such as post-its, sharpies, and pens were provided for completing the A0 canvases and support action prioritization. Sign-in sheets for participants and guidance documents for facilitators were printed as well. The workshop made use of the designated exhibition space provided by Thessaloniki International Fair (TIF). Digital presentations were conducted using Mentimeter, a projector, a laptop, and the required sound equipment. Catering services were provided, offering beverages and snacks to the attendees. To ensure attendee comfort, tables and chairs were arranged in a manner that facilitated the seating of three groups.

Participants

The workshop was attended by a total of 22 participants excluding project partners, presenting a well-balanced distribution in terms of gender, with a slightly higher representation of women. A broad range of quadruple helix stakeholders was represented, specifically 8 policy makers, 8 business/industry representatives, 4 researchers and academics, as well as 2 civil society representatives. This inclusive composition aligns with the quadruple helix model, which emphasizes the involvement of diverse stakeholders in research and innovation endeavors.

Results from introductory session (project presentation + baseline monitoring survey)

In the beginning of the workshop, Margarita Angelidou (QPL) presented briefly the purposes and activities of the ROBIN project and the agenda of the workshop. For this purpose, a power point presentation was prepared by QPL based on the template developed by CTA. This was followed by a session dedicated to a baseline monitoring survey. During this session QPL asked participants to answer several questions about the current situation in the Central Macedonia region regarding circular bioeconomy and the relevant governance models. Participants' answers were captured by the mentimeter platform and directly appear on the screen (Figure 27), giving the opportunity to discuss them further. The questions asked and the results are presented in detail below.

Table 4. Central Macedonia baseline results

	Question	Result
1	What is your current type of involvement in the regional bioeconomy sector?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am a policymaker = 5 • I am a researcher or academic = 8 • I am a representative of the business community = 3 • I am a representative of a non-governmental or civil society organization = 1 • Other = 3
2	How would you describe the level of development of the bioeconomy in your region?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very advanced = 0 • Somewhat advanced = 0 • Moderate = 7 • Limited = 12 • Non-existent or very low = 2
3	How effective do you think the current bioeconomy context (regulatory, business, etc) is in achieving regional development goals?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very effective = 0 • Somewhat effective = 2 • Neutral = 7 • somewhat ineffective = 5 • Very ineffective = 3 • Not applicable = 2
4	What steps do you think can be taken to improve the effectiveness of regional bioeconomy context?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase funding for bioeconomy initiatives = 17 • Enhance stakeholder engagement = 17 • Streamline regulatory processes = 16 • Develop better infrastructure = 11 • Other (please specify) = 1
5	How well does your bioeconomy context promote sustainable development and environmental protection?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very well = 0 • Well = 6 • Moderately = 4 • Poorly = 8 • Very poorly = 2 • Not applicable = 1
6	How well does your bioeconomy context foster innovation and the development of new technologies and products in the bioeconomy sector?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very well = 0 • Well = 4 • Moderately = 5 • Poorly = 9 • Very poorly = 2 • Not applicable = 0

7	How well does your region perform in identifying and grasping opportunities for innovative, sustainable circular business models in your region?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very well = 1 • Well = 3 • Moderately = 7 • Poorly = 4 • Very poorly = 4 • Not applicable = 2
8	How well does your region perform in developing social innovations addressing local needs?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very well = 2 • Well = 3 • Moderately = 14 • Poorly = 2 • Very poorly = 0 • Not applicable = 0
9	How well does the bioeconomy context ensures the participation and engagement of relevant stakeholders (e.g., government, business community, civil society, academia, local communities, etc.)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very effectively = 0 • Effectively = 10 • Moderately = 7 • Ineffectively = 3 • Very ineffectively = 1 • Not applicable = 0
10	Do you know or use some efficient tools that can be used when designing, implementing or monitoring initiatives to promote bioeconomy? Please provide some examples	Horizon Europe, European regional development fund, Funding for teaching bioeconomy to adults, One stop liaison office, other national or European funding schemes,

The above answers reveal that most of the invited stakeholders believe that bioeconomy is still in an infancy status in the region of Central Macedonia. Moreover, the regulatory, policy, business and other context are minimally facilitating the transition towards a bioeconomy. The stakeholders identified several key steps that they deemed crucial, including increasing the size of funding schemes, enhancing collaboration among stakeholders and updating the regulatory framework. These responses were collected through a questionnaire administered through Mentimeter.

Figure 27. Baseline Monitoring Survey-presenting Mentimeter results

Results from session 1 (regional analysis: background, potential of biomass and SWOT analysis)

Kallitsa Pantazi (RCM) welcomed all the attendees and informed them about the project's agenda and what the event entails. Margarita Angelidou (QPL) and Alexandros Skondras (AUPh) introduced themselves and the rest of their teammates which are involved in the ROBIN project. Margarita Angelidou presented ROBIN's scope, what has been accomplished so far as well as the project's future steps (Figure 28). Dimitrios Vlachos (RCM) gave the regional overview presentation where the attendees learned of the bioeconomy of the Region of Central Macedonia, its strengths, barriers and needed actions. There were no questions throughout the PowerPoint presentation. Then, Margarita Angelidou guided the attendees to complete a baseline monitoring survey with the use of mentimeter. Moreover, she explained and commented on the results and gave concluding remarks.

Figure 28. ROBIN project introduction and regional context for Region of Central Macedonia

Results from session 2

For Session 2, Aikaterini Bakousi (AUPh) presented a warm-up exercise with the participants for the collection of meaningful insights on the biomass feedstocks in the region, in which participants provided information and knowledge on the subject. Aikaterini Bakousi requested from the participants to split into 3 groups and provide 5 types of biomasses and their knowledge on them. The 3 groups exchanged ideas and provided numerous answers. The results of this exercise showed that the Region of Central Macedonia is known for its diverse biomass feedstocks that contribute to renewable energy production and sustainable development. Here are some common biomass feedstocks found in the region:

- Agricultural Residues
- Forest Biomass
- Energy Crops
- Organic Waste
- Agro-Industrial Byproducts

In particular, the participants highlighted that coffee residues, urban waste, sewage sludge, olive kernels, animal waste, frying oil, food waste are used for energy production (e.g., biodiesel). In addition, pruning from urban spaces or shellfish shells are used for compost; pine extract for cosmetics; and biological wastewater management for irrigation.

Alexandros Skondras (AUTH) then presented the co-creation framework for circular bioeconomy and explained the exercise regarding the prioritization of the support actions to the group, giving instructions to the guests and explaining what was required for the prioritization. The attendees were then asked to rate 5 preselected regional actions depending on their significance (1 being the most important, 5 being the least important). Finally, a discussion on the resulting ranking took place.

Alexandros Skondras then presented the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas to the group. He went through each section of the canvas, providing examples for the participants and explaining what was required for each box. He provided further information on the bioeconomy pillars that should be kept in mind while completing the canvas. The 3 groups then began working through the canvas, providing answers specific to the Region of Central Macedonia. Alexandros Skondras, Aikaterini Bakousi and Ifigeneia Skalidi (AUTH) led the discussion on each table of attendees and assisted with the completion of the canvas. Each team discussed thoroughly and exchanged very innovative ideas. The workshop was concluded by Ifigeneia Skalidi, Alexandros Skondras and Aikaterini Bakousi who each presented the table's results.

With regards to the feedback for the bioeconomy governance canvas: Overall, the co-creation of the canvas went very well, the participants were satisfied, and we got very interesting results. It was helpful that we filled in 3 different canvases – we got a wealth of diverse and interesting ideas. For the value proposition section: The section didn't stand out in the canvas. In this field, the participants were asked to mention the potential environmental/economic/social benefits for the society (in the long run). However, there was no particular field asking about objectives and desired outcomes (in short and medium term). Thus, there was little discussion about the purposes, identity and motivation behind the suggested value proposition. For the activities section: In some cases, participants were unsure about how general or specific the definitions of the activities should be. For the rest of the sections: Sometimes there was an overlap (or at least not very clear distinction) between two fields (e.g., resources and infrastructure), and the last two categories (regional development requirements and policy) could be merged into one. In general, the canvas is quite elaborated for someone and the canvas sections could be also interconnected as many sections overlapped.

After this, concluding remarks were finally given by Margarita Angelidou (QPL). The attendees also completed a feedback form and were all very engaged and enthusiastic to further get to know each other and also follow the project's future results.

Figure 29. Working sessions on biomass feedstocks

Figure 30. Working sessions on co-creation framework and CANVAS

Satisfaction survey results

At the end of the workshop, participants were asked to fill in a satisfaction survey. All of them expressed their high satisfaction with the organisation of the workshop, the relevance of the topic, the quality and clarity of the speakers, the level of the dialogue with the audience and the usefulness of the regional governance canvas tool used.

	Question	Answers
Please, evaluate the following aspects of the event (1=poor, 5 = excellent)	Organisation	4.94
	Relevance of the topic and content	4.94
	Level of the speakers (quality and clarity)	4.82
	Participation and dialogue with the audience	4.88
	Usefulness of the REGIONAL GOVERNANCE CANVAS tool used in the event	4.94
Where did you hear about this event	Social Media	11%
	e-mail / Newsletter	17%
	EU Green Week website	0%
	Direct invitation	56%
	Other	17%

Macedonia regional governance model

The context

The information presented in the current section has been gathered and reproduced from the Deliverable D1.3 “Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of the ROBIN Regions”¹.

The Region of Central Macedonia has an area of 19,146 sq.km, which represents 14,5% of the total area size of Greece. The population is approximately 1.7 million according to the 2021 census results and is growing at a steady rate. The second most populated city of Greece, Thessaloniki, is located in the Region, along with a network of large towns. The territory is a mix of urban, peri-urban, semi-rural & rural areas.

When it comes to the implementation of circular bioeconomy in the Region of Central Macedonia, the priority and potential regional sectors/value chains for the circular bioeconomy are: 1. Agriculture, 2. Livestock, 3. Agroindustry, 4. Chemical industry and 5. Energy. The territorial sensitivity of the Region of Central Macedonia is extremely high. A sustainable and circular bioeconomy contributes to addressing global challenges e.g., climate change, land & ecosystem degradation, which combined with a growing demand for food, feed & energy, results to new ways of producing & consuming. Thus, industries simultaneously modernize their production systems & protect the environment.

Circular bioeconomy in the Region of Central Macedonia is presently “making its first steps”. The implementation of circular bioeconomy affects the region to a great extent. Its effect is important on positive environmental terms (less emissions of CO₂, less water consumption, soil fertility). Its societal effect is strongly positive because of its increased rate of employment in relevant sectors, especially in agriculture, waste management & energy. Economically, Circular Bioeconomy will also result to a positive effect as its development is creating a climate that promotes the development and modernization of new start-ups and other enterprises.

Recently, the Regional Development Fund on behalf of the Region of Central Macedonia participated in the European scheme “Regional Models of circular economy & best available techniques for biological streams” – BIOREGIO, funded by the interregional programme INTERREG EUROPE 2014-2020. BIOREGIO’s target has been the direction of regional policies to support the best practices of circular economy. It was implemented locally by the Heat Transfer & Environmental Engineering Laboratory of the Department of Mechanical Engineers of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and the Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia. CESME (Circular Economy for SMEs) was another interregional cooperation programme funded by INTERREG EUROPE 2014-2020, which concluded recently. It aimed to support the transition from a linear to a circular economy where all outflows from a production activity are reused as inflows to another production activity.

Through a SWOT analysis that was performed for the Region of Central Macedonia the following results came to light:

- Strengths: There are services from both the government & public sector to continuously increase knowledge about Circular Bioeconomy. There are management systems to enhance knowledge & implementation to increase e.g., recycling. There is a good presence of consulting engineering companies. There is significant development of waste-to-energy

¹ ROBIN Consortium, 2023, Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, pp.131-136.

plants e.g., biogas plants. There is a great production capacity of biomass resources from agriculture, livestock production, agri-food, forest and fishing sectors.

- **Weakness:** There are no Regional Bioeconomy Governance Models in place. There is a lack of obligatory systems & mechanisms for monitoring, reviewing & evaluating the results of small enterprises that can actually improve their productivity. Farmers' focus on their compensations and not on increasing their skills in agriculture management. There is over consolidated use of several plants resulting to exclusion of others. There is a limited knowledge on the characteristics of a great variety of biomass resources with potential as raw material for the production of innovative bioproducts.
- **Opportunities:** There is available European funding to help farmers and industries to incorporate and implement new systems/techniques/processes, as well as governmental funding. The opening of the market could develop new intra- European trade & business opportunities. There is growing interest for sustainable investment.
- **Threats:** There is a potential negative consequence of increasing biomass use on other aspects of society. There is a reduction of the biomass resources available due to the effects of climate change. Livelihood and daily life problems are the main concern of the entrepreneurs (farmers, plant owners), more than the integration of new technologies & circular bioeconomy approaches. There are bureaucratic burdens and excessive administrative procedures that entail important obstacles for entrepreneurship.

Identification of the regional Governance Model improvement areas

Within the co-creation framework, several actions were identified and prioritized as being of particular importance to feed into the support actions and the overall regional vision identified for the Region of Central Macedonia. Five support actions were chosen from the partners and are summarized below.

Ensure Food & nutrition security - Food security and nutrition supported.

Manage natural resources sustainably - Ecosystem capacity to produce services is maintained or enhanced.

Reduce dependence on unsustainable resources - Resource efficiency improved.

Mitigate & adapt to climate change - Climate change mitigation and adaptation are pursued.

Strengthen European competitiveness & create jobs - Economic development fostered.

During the workshop, the participants were asked to assign a significance rating (with 1 being the most important and 5 being the least important) to the five preselected regional actions. The results of the prioritization indicated that the first three actions (**Ensure Food & nutrition security** - Food security and nutrition supported, **manage natural resources sustainably** - Ecosystem capacity to produce services is maintained or enhanced, **reduce dependence on unsustainable resources** - Resource efficiency improved) were deemed the most important for the development of the circular bioeconomy in the Region of Central Macedonia. The fourth action (**Mitigate & adapt to climate change** - Climate change mitigation and adaptation are pursued) received conflicting rankings, with one of the three co-creation tables considering it a top priority, while the remaining tables ranked it as a lower priority. The fifth action (**Strengthen European competitiveness & create jobs** - Economic development fostered) was generally regarded as either the least important or the second least important by the participants.

Regional Vision: Through consultation and discussion between all Region of Central Macedonia ROBIN partners (RCM, AUTh, QPL), an objective was agreed upon, which would be achievable and

at the same time deliver practical results. The regional vision proposed was the 'Development of Bioeconomy Cluster in Central Macedonia with all actors. The principal outcomes and results of this regional vision were also evident when the canvas was completed and illustrated the environmental, economic, and social benefits of a structured circular bioeconomy policy for the region, as well as providing key baseline data regarding what and how this vision can be implemented in the context of a novel bioeconomy governance strategy in the region.

Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Results

1. **Regional Vision / Value Proposition:** As mentioned in the previous section, through collaboration an objective of the **Development of Bioeconomy Cluster in Central Macedonia with all actors** was decided upon as the regional vision. This value proposition will inform a cohesive regional circular bioeconomy policy which includes *Environmental Benefits*, such as improvements to waste management, improvements to ecological sustainability, reduction of pollutants through biomass and balanced exploitation and sustainable management of bioeconomic resources. The *Economic benefits* identified from the value proposition include more EU funds, better energy efficiency and the limitation of brain drainage as well as new job openings and social and environmental inclusion in taxation. *Social Benefits* will include education on regional policy and proper education to responsible citizens, better welfare and a better level of social security, development of extra income with recycling actions, clean atmosphere and better health, as well as the prioritization of incentives to create healthy relationships.

2. **Activities:** Ten support activities were chosen and were considered as the initial steps that should be considered to support the delivery of the value proposition.

- Opening event of the cluster.
- Search for financing tools and member information.
- Creation of a digital platform.
- Promotion (marketing campaign) of energy communities.
- Recruitment of various members.
- Development of a strategic vision.
- Establishment of an office for specialization in bioeconomy.
- Establishment of a joint venture between the partners of the cluster.
- Establishment of educational programs.
- Definition of a regional information and training plan focusing on targeting and mentoring (consultancy).

3. **Partnerships:** The actors that are required to collaborate in order to execute the regional vision were identified within the workshop and are in line with the quadruple helix model as follows:

- Sustainable neighbourhoods / citizens.
- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / University of Macedonia.
- Citizen science associations.
- FODSA (Solid waste management body).
- Forest departments.
- Municipalities and Region of Central Macedonia.
- Ministry of Energy.
- Cooperative Symbiosis.
- Other similar clusters.
- European and international bioeconomy networks.
- Volunteers.
- Consumers associations.

- NGOs.

4. **Resources:** The unique resources that are available to the Region of Central Macedonia and mentioned in the workshop were mainly:

- National resources.
- EU resources.
- Biomass feedstocks.
- Partnerships with the quadruple helix actors mentioned in the partnerships section.
- Public & Private Sector Partnerships.
- Financial resources through MIP/CIP.
- Mapping of bioavailability.
- Provision of technological means.
- Sponsorships.

5. **Infrastructure:** The Region of Central Macedonia can benefit from the following infrastructure. In order to support the development of the bioeconomy:

- Biogas and bioenergy units.
- Pilot units (e.g., compost units and units for the production and pouring of biomethane).
- Commitment to publicity and transparency with the implementation of the digital platform.
- Marketplace for producers + exchange of tools.
- Technical infrastructure.
- Possibility for all users to propose innovation and new tools.
- Living Labs.

6. **Regional Actors / Stakeholders:** those better suited for the regional vision are the quadruple helix stakeholders. Regional actors and stakeholders that can foster the development in the region are mainly:

- Academia / Research.
- Industry / Businesses.
- Citizens.
- Municipalities / Regions
- NGOs.
- Cooperatives.
- Chambers.

7. **Regional Relationships:** The development of relationships with all the stakeholders is crucial. Within the workshop, numerous methods were identified to achieve this. According to the participants the main relationships could be consolidated and fostered by:

- Dissemination of the cluster.
- Co-creation workshops.
- Bioeconomy festivals and activities.
- Cultural events (such as this one).
- Creation of infrastructure within the cluster by topic.
- Improvement of available channels for communication.
- Creation of a cluster board with all kinds of stakeholders.
- Leveraging relationships with the university.

8. **Channels:** The manner in which the information around the regional vision gets to the 'outside world' was also explored within the canvas during the workshop. The following methods appear to have a major impact for the attendees:

- Site / social media.
- Newsletters.

- Flyers.
- Word of mouth.
- Workshops.
- Call for organizations to record good practices.

9. **Regional Development Requirements:** The way in which the regional vision should be implemented was also explored. The participants believe that the following requirements play a paramount role in the development of the regional vision:

- Qualified human resources.
- Qualified management personnel.
- Education for the region employees.
- Education for the citizens.
- Establishment of primary chambers of commerce
- Region contribution to networking
- Region contribution to working spaces.

10. **Regional Development Policy / Outcomes:** The anticipated policy development requirements or benefits required to deliver the vision, include:

- Independence of resources.
- Added value in production chains.
- Incentives to citizens for their participation in the support actions.
- Recruiting experts and creating jobs.
- Development of the converge of capabilities between actors.
- Waste management legislation.

For the complete bioeconomy governance canvas, see Annex 7.

Southern Region regional event

Southern Region regional event organization

Official event title

ROBIN Southern Region Co-Creation Event

Regional customisation

The event was held in English and the agenda changed slightly on the day. MTU and SRA decided to introduce ROBIN first and then go straight into the warmup baseline survey. The Irish ROBIN Team did this as we felt it was important for our attendees to answer the survey uninfluenced before hearing the Southern Region overview. As the Southern Region overview contained detailed information on the circular bioeconomy in the region, we wanted to ensure this information would not impact our guest's thoughts. The team felt this would provide more accurate results from the baseline survey.

During the ROBIN presentation, we adapted the format slightly to also include some of the project's findings from the previous deliverables to show our guests some of the work already completed within the project.

Rather than breaking for coffee after session 1, we decided to go straight into the Regional Analysis discussion. We chose to do this very last minute as we felt we had the focused attention of the group and there was no real need for a break at this stage. This worked well, and we all agreed this was best for the flow of the workshop.

We then presented our prefilled SWOT but also provided each attendee with their own blank SWOT for them to fill in and add to what we had already selected.

One final change that occurred on the day was the presenting of the feedback survey. Initially, we had prepared the Feedback Survey on Mentimeter, just as we had done with the Baseline Monitoring Survey. However, the baseline survey took longer than expected. People had trouble with the QR codes, often forgetting to submit their answers correctly and so this took up a lot of time. As the work on the canvas had taken longer than expected also, we made a snap decision to provide the feedback survey on paper to gather these answers and it turned out to be much faster.

Agenda

Co-creation Workshop Agenda

Date: 10/05/2023 | **Location:** Cork

Venue: [Nimbus Seminar Room at MTU - Cork Campus, Bishopstown](#)

Time	Topic
1.00-1.45	Light Lunch in Nimbus Library
1.45-2.00	Southern Region Overview
2.00-2.15	ROBIN Presentation
2.15-2.30	Workshop Warm-up
2.30-2.45	Break for Coffee
2.45-3.00	Regional Analysis Discussion
3.00-3.10	Guidance for the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas
3.10-4.10	Working session on Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas
4.10-4.30	Wrap-up Session

Figure 31. Official agenda

Date, host, registration and venue

Date: 10th May 2023

Host: Munster Technological University and Southern Regional Assembly

Registration: Eventbrite - <https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/robin-southern-region-co-creation-event-tickets-611043436367>

Venue: Nimbus Seminar Room, MTU, Cork

Figure 32. Workshop attendees

Figure 33. ROBIN workshop in progress

Required equipment, material, and logistics.

In preparation for the event, we had 5 blank A0 ROBIN circular bioeconomy governance models canvases printed out along with 1 A0 canvas with prefilled examples. We also had 3 A3 examples printed out to provide to each of our 3 groups as guidance. We had ROBIN pamphlets printed along with a ROBIN pop up stand. 2 Southern Regional Assembly pop up stands were brought along with 1 large MTU pop up stand. Reusable event goody bags were prepared by the Southern Regional Assembly which included pens, notebooks, indigenous Irish wild flour seeds, mints, bicycle cover etc. Post-its, sharpies, pens etc., were brought to complete the canvas/SWOT. The blank SWOT sheets were printed as well as both Mentimeter surveys (in case of technology issues), the agenda, the participant sign in sheet and some guidance documents for the facilitators to use if needed during the co-creation of the canvas. We made sure everyone attending had name tags and brought spare name tags just in case. Our presentations and both Mentimeter surveys were preprepared and we used 2 laptops throughout the day. The venue provided lunch, beverages, and snacks. We decided to set the tables and chairs up into 3 groups from the very beginning to avoid moving furniture in the middle of the event.

Participants

13 registered persons were representatives from different types of organisations. More specifically, the following participants from across the quadruple model helix were present: 2 policy makers, 4 researchers and academics, 2 civil society representatives and 3 representatives from business and SME.

Results from introductory session (project presentation + baseline monitoring survey)

James Gaffey started the day off with the ROBIN presentation, delivered via PowerPoint and projected onto a white screen at the event venue. The general presentation provided by White Research was adapted for the event and James spoke for 15 minutes on ROBIN's objectives, regions, work packages and next steps. He also provided a brief update on the work already completed by the ROBIN partners in Work package 1. This was a fantastic addition as it provided a general idea of the best practices from other countries/initiatives.

Next, we moved on to the baseline monitoring survey to gauge our guests understanding of the bioeconomy in the region. A QR code was used for the attendees to access Mentimeter and delivered the survey. This took longer than expected as some guests had technical issues, and some were unsure how to use the tool.

Baseline Monitoring Survey results:

Figure 34. Southern Region baseline presentation

For the final question, most of our guests did not know or use any efficient tools that can be used when designing, implementing or monitoring bioeconomy governance models. One suggestion we received was the European Bioeconomy Monitoring Platform.

Results from session 1 (regional analysis: background, potential of biomass and SWOT analysis)

Rebecca Walsh gave the regional overview presentation where the attendees learned of the bioeconomy of the Southern Region, it's strengths, barriers and needed actions. There were no questions throughout the PowerPoint presentation. Robert Ludgate then presented the prefilled Southern Region SWOT Analysis. While discussing the opportunities of the region, Robert spoke of the potential of biomass in the region and what biomass resources the region has.

Next, we provided our attendees with a blank SWOT and we sat with them at each table and had an open discussion about additional strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that they felt we could add.

We think this worked effectively as it got people thinking and got them engaged and prepared for further collaboration on the canvas.

Although our groups agreed with our prefilled SWOT, attendants had much more to add to it, in particular in the Opportunities box.

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESESS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good interaction between bioeconomy Stakeholders • Access to EU funding and projects, lots of projects • Just Transition • Small Island in terms of connectivity with good infrastructure • Biomass/forestry resources • Industry buy-in • Green Image – high on the agenda • Co-operative Structure • Innovation culture • Farm C is a good example of a successful bioeconomy project from research • Growth of SECs – Sustainable Energy Communities • Strong Industrial Sectors-Pharma, Biomedical, agrifood • Public RSES supports the Circular Bioeconomy. • Establishment of clusters in the region including Circular Bioeconomy Cluster South West and Irish Bioeconomy Foundation. • Strong regional R&D and educational activities in the region. • Political commitment (National Policy Statement on Bioeconomy, Bioeconomy Action Plan 2023-2025). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long planning application times and costs, strict planning regulation • No existing specialist industry meaning higher costs for infrastructure • Weak regional tier of government with limited staff/resources • Poor community engagement/understanding • Finance – lack of access and knowledge • Lack of public procurement programme • Lack of demo sites • No monitoring framework • Access to knowledge about commodity markets • No Regional Bioeconomy Governance in place. • Lack of connectivity between relevant stakeholders in the region

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding is available, better help to access • Single access point to access knowledge • Develop group/sustainable business models • Marine sector is under utilised • Massive demand for green gas – financial supports needed • Highlight the success of existing projects • Local industry • Existing food/Bioeconomy Structures • Shared Ireland Initiative • Biopharma/biomedical • Planning reform • Alignment with 'fit for 55' targets • Horticulture • Plant protein • Lisheen • Local authorities to engage with communities • Digitalisation • Engagement, Education and outreach • Green certificates • Upskilling/reskilling • Identify targets • Policy needs to be driven • Bioeconomy as a service • Rewilding • More tourism sector engagement/contribution • Growing interest for sustainability/net zero • Awareness raising • Develop more efficient biomass uses • Biomass: Mushroom Compost, Spent Grain, Whey, Cheese, high value bio plastic, Cereal, Seaweed, Forestry, Green Waste – Grass/Civic waste, Agro-processing Sidestreams • Brewing- towards higher value end use over low value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of bioeconomy in primary production, seen as threat • EPA inflexibility on licenses • Administration loads and delays of planning • Price competitiveness of fossil fuels especially fossil gas • Lack of shared vision • Global conflict/rising prices • Misinformation • Finance needed • Inflexibility of primary producers to change • Potential negative consequence of increasing biomass use on other aspects of society • Outdated Regulatory Environment – inappropriate for modern bioeconomy • Effective substitutes

Figure 35. ROBIN workshop in progress

Results from session 2

For Session 2, Robert Ludgate presented the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas to the group. He went through each section of the canvas, providing examples for our guests and explaining what was required for each box. He provided further information on the bioeconomy pillars that should be kept in mind while completing the canvas. Our 3 groups then began working through the canvas, providing answers specific to the Southern Region. Some feedback while we worked through the canvas was that it might be clearer to rename certain headings or to combine them. Another guest felt that the canvas might be more beneficial if we were to choose a more specific element of the bioeconomy e.g., Anaerobic digestion and fill out the canvas in relation to this. We explained this task was to get an overview of the bioeconomy as a whole but he felt it could be more productive to have a more centred topic.

The main take away from this session is that more time was needed to diagnose the bioeconomy of the Southern Region to complete the canvas.

After this, we handed out our feedback survey and then gave a brief overview of ROBIN's next steps regarding the ROBIN toolbox.

Lastly, we had the ROBIN QR code enlarged on our screen for attendees to follow our ROBIN social media pages.

Figure 36. ROBIN workshop in progress

Satisfaction survey results

8 of our 11 attendees completed our feedback survey on the day. 100% of our surveyed participants felt the organisation of the event was excellent. For 'Relevance of the topic and content', 'Level of speakers (quality and clarity)' and 'Participation and dialogue with the audience', 37.5% of our guests felt these were good with the remaining group rating them excellent. In terms of the 'Usefulness of the regional governance canvas tool used at the event', 57% surveyed believed the canvas was excellent. 29% scored the canvas as very good with the remaining vote labelling the canvas good.

Attendees felt the event was well organised, engaging, and interactive. A common theme in the feedback section was that there was not enough time to complete the canvas and that there was room for improvement over time. Some questions raised were - Will the tool be effective? Will it influence the right people? Is it too technical/not accessible enough? Are the headings clear enough?

I received an email after the event also comparing governance structures to Co-operative structures.

“Co-operative structure presents a proven model to involve primary producers and communities in the bioeconomy. This model is relatively simple, with a standardised template rule book and integral governance training, guidance, and ongoing support for co-operative board members. There are a lot of entrepreneurs operating in this space, the majority are very innovative and positive additions whilst others may be more exploitative of those who possess less power as individuals but could benefit from democratic collaborative organisation through co-operative structure. Co-operatives not only afford economies of scale, bargaining power, and a fair and equal say for all members, they also provide a centralised platform to engage with policy, funding and other stakeholders”.

Figure 37. ROBIN workshop in progress

Southern Region, Ireland regional governance model

The context

When it comes to the implementation of the circular bioeconomy in the Southern Region, it would be classified as being of mixed maturity. Located on the western edge of Europe, this region encompasses over 42% of Irish state territory. The population is approximately 1.7 million according to the 2022 census results, representing one third of the state’s population, and is growing at a steady rate that is projected to continue, reaching almost 2 million by 2040 according to the Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy for the region. Three out of Ireland’s five cities, Cork, Limerick and Waterford, are in the Region along with a network of large towns. In 2020, it was classified as a ‘more developed region’.

The region is abundant in naturally occurring renewable feedstocks. The most abundant of these feedstocks include grasses, cattle manure and slurry, food production wastes or side streams, meat and bone meals, cattle industry wastes, pig and chicken manure and cereal straws. Also, within the region are smaller (but growing) amounts of energy crops, horticultural residues such as mushroom compost as well as residues from the forestry industry like woodchips and sawmill residues. Due to the long coastline of the region, there is also an availability of biomass and waste streams from the blue/marine economy as well the biomass available from seaweed. Biobased urban waste can also be considered available and open to exploitation as the region encompasses 3 of Irelands major cities as well as an array of other smaller population centres.

At a regulatory level, the Southern Region has numerous regulatory documents that are influencing and supporting the development of a circular bioeconomy without the presence of a specific regional circular bioeconomy strategy. At a national level, the National Policy Statement on the Bioeconomy is part of a broader bioeconomy strategy for the country and was one of the precursors to the Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy 2022 – 2023 and was Ireland’s first national circular economy strategy. At a regional level the Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy (RSES) which was

developed by ROBIN regional partners The Southern Regional Assembly contains specific Regional Policy Objectives (RPOs) relating to circular bioeconomy development. The Regional Approach for development of a Smart Specialisation Strategy in the Southern identifies the circular bioeconomy as a key sector for the region with further priority areas identified to direct resources towards and The Southern Region Waste Management Plan 2015-2021 identifies development of effective waste management strategies and moving towards circularity as an important issue for achieving climate mitigation goals.

During the workshop, a SWOT analysis was performed for the Southern Region and was particularly useful in providing a clear high-level perspective on what the Southern Region has to its advantage as well as areas that can be engaged with to continue development of the circular bioeconomy.

Strengths: The region already is identified as having good interaction and communication between stakeholders, with good industry buy-in and a strong innovation culture. This culture arises from an active circular bioeconomy research and education sector driven by activities at Munster Technological University, The Irish Bioeconomy Foundation amongst others within the region. Farm Zero C is a strong example of an initiative that has arisen through industry buy-in and collaboration with research institutions.

Weakness: Also identified were several inherent weaknesses, such as long planning application times and costs involved within strict planning within the region that can at times slow down development. Crucial to any development in any sector is the access to finance and this was clearly identified as a crucial aspect to be overcome as well as the knowledge of how to access existing funding available to development of the circular bioeconomy.

Opportunities: Whilst the circular bioeconomy can be at a mixed level of maturity, the marine / blue economy was identified as being significantly underutilised while it was also suggested that greater interaction and engagement with biopharmaceutical and biomedical industries is needed. According to the stakeholders, bioeconomy successes need to be better promoted either through a greater use of practical examples such as demonstration units or the publication and dissemination of success story case studies as illustrations of what has been and can be achieved.

Threats: Perhaps one of the most significant threats to further development is the lack of knowledge of the circular bioeconomy among primary producers and industry. Thus, information dissemination and education are important again in developing a shared vision and overcoming the sometimes inflexibility of primary producers to adapt to change. The issue of whether the circular bioeconomy can deliver effective substitutes to fossil-based products at a competitive cost were also identified as a long-term threat to development of the sector within the region.

Full details of the SWOT analysis carried out within the workshop can be found in Annex 8.

Identification of the regional Governance Model improvement areas

Within the framework, several actions were identified and prioritized as being of particular importance to both addressing the weakness and threats recognised within the SWOT analysis and feeding into the support actions and the overall regional vision identified for the Southern Region. The most relevant points from the workshop are summarized below.

Managing Natural Resources Sustainably: This one of the key actions of the framework and perhaps the most overarching factor as it can contribute to several of the support actions, particularly as the region has a large primary production sector (agriculture, marine, forestry etc.). Ensuring that primary

production sectors are managed sustainably, and their coordinated sustainable management is an important aspect of future of the circular bioeconomy within the region.

Reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad: Identified within the SWOT analysis as a key threat to the future development of the circular bioeconomy, the areas of resource efficiency, sustainable production and consumption of biomass and bio-based products and the sustainability of urban centres become important driving factors to both the support actions and the regional vision.

Mitigating and adapting to climate change: The importance of climate change mitigation and adaption was noted as key to policy development for the region, and it is therefore important to ensure the regional activities align and contribute to this objective.

Strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs: Within the RSES document, the Southern Regional assembly have identified regional competitiveness and job creation as a key aspect. Development of the circular bioeconomy will play a large part in delivering this. The regional vision will help ensure that economic development is fostered in an inclusive manner, promoting resilience of the rural, coastal, and urban economies.

- 1) **Regional Vision:** Through consultation and discussion between both Southern Region ROBIN partners (SRA & MTU), an objective was agreed upon, which would be achievable and at the same time deliver practical results. The regional vision proposed was a Working Document to inform Regional Circular Bioeconomy & Structures. This document can serve as a building block for the further development of a regional circular bioeconomy policy for the Southern Region. The benefits of this holistic type of working document were also evident as once completed it will illustrate the environmental, economic, and social benefits of a structured circular bioeconomy policy to the region. It will also provide key baseline data regarding where the region sits with regards to key aspects of the bioeconomy such as skills, funding mechanisms etc.

Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Results

1. Regional Vision / Value Proposition: As mentioned in the previous section, through collaboration an objective of **A Working Document to inform Regional Circular Bioeconomy & Structures** was decided upon as the regional vision. This value proposition will inform a cohesive regional circular bioeconomy policy which includes *Environmental Benefits*, such as improvements to Air and Water quality, coordinated climate change mitigation, sustainable management of natural resources and a more cohesive spatial planning. The *Economic benefits* identified from the value proposition include alternative incomes for primary producers, particularly within the agricultural sector and this diversification could lead to reduced risk in their future activities. In addition, the development of regionally produced biobased alternative to existing imported fossil-based products will not only drive regional research and development but also play a large factor in regional and rural economic growth. *Social Benefits* will include greater energy security for the region as more biobased alternatives are developed locally. The development of this and other biobased startups will help in the development of greater value chain development, more employment in the sector and a cohesive circular bioeconomy policy for the region will drive a just transition and mitigate any adverse outcome from the transition to biobased business models.

2. Activities: Ten support activities were chosen and were considered as the initial steps that should be considered to support the delivery of the value proposition.

- Establish Steering Committee > Collaboration on document.

- Engage Bioeconomy Stakeholders > Coordination map / framework.
- Education Building > Mapping & Review of current landscape
- Engage with Local Authorities > Review / gaps in engagement.
- Bioeconomy Awareness > Develop outreach plan (bioeconomy week).
- Regional Bioeconomy research > Identify underutilized research areas.
- Business/SME Bioeconomy> Identify matchmaking opportunities.
- Bioeconomy Funding assist > Identify underutilized funding mechanisms.
- Evaluate Governance Structures / Policies suitable for Southern Region.
- Strategy Implementation > Examination of level (nuts 2/nuts 3).

3. Partnerships: The actors that that are required to collaborate to execute the regional vision were identified within the workshops and are in line with the quadruple helix model as follows.

- Government – Regional Authorities, Local Authorities (Particularly the LEO offices) and other regulatory bodies.
- Industry – Primary Producers (Farming, Fisheries & Forestry Groups) Representative groups like ICOS.
- Academia & Research - i.e., MTU, UCD, SETU, TUS and Teagasc
- Community – Local Development Communities i.e., Leader Groups etc.

4. Resources: The unique resources that are available to the Southern Region of Ireland were identified within the workshop and as previously mentioned in section 2.1 are plentiful to the region and is a primary reason to further develop a circular bioeconomy strategy within the region. Outside of the availability of the numerous feedstocks, there is the possibility of the numerous residue streams from food processing, agriculture, and alcohol manufacturing and well as the established body of knowledge and expertise that exists within academia in the region.

5. Infrastructure: The Southern Region also benefits from existing infrastructure with the region that can be used to support the development of the bioeconomy. The primary example is the Bioeconomy Campus as Lisheen in county Tipperary. Established on a disused mine site, it is already home to the Irish Bioeconomy Foundation and boasts the availability of nearly 1000 acres and can be seen a planned location asset. Other established infrastructural assets within the region include access to the national gas grid, wastewater treatment plants, numerous ‘brownfield’ sites and an extensive road and port infrastructure across the region. The ‘Greening’ of existing industry should also be considered such as Whitegate refinery in Cork and the various industries at Foynes in Limerick.

6. Regional Actors / Stakeholders: those who are involved in delivering the regional vision were identified as The SRA through it’s work on the RSES policy document and the respective local authorities across the region. The Irish Bioenergy Association was considered that it could play an important part as well as the various agricultural bodies like ICOS, Teagasc and the Irish Farmers Association (IFA). Educational and research institutions were again identified as playing an important part here and well as engagement with private industry and SMEs.

7. Regional Relationships: The development of relationships with all the stakeholders is crucial. Within the workshop, numerous methods were identified to achieve this. Stakeholder and public outreach were seen as important. Using methods such as information events / seminars, workshops and conferences will foster these relationships. Also, it was seen as important that existing relationships between the SRA and local authorities be further advanced.

8. Channels: The manner in which the information around the regional vision gets to the ‘outside world’ was also explored within the canvas during the workshop. Appointing Local Champions was seen as a novel way to help get the message of the circular bioeconomy to the public as well as appointing trusted information providers that can educate and inform. The use of local knowledge

was also seen as valuable. An attendee within the workshop suggested a 'bioeconomy booklet' that would have a concise amount of information, that could include general circular bioeconomy information and could be the first point of contact with the public.

9. Regional Development Requirements: The way in which the regional vision should be implemented was also explored. Education featured predominately again, and it was considered important that developing the bioeconomy should feed into educational programmes at all levels of education within the region, primary, secondary, and at third level. A skilled workforce, educated with knowledge and skills to meet the needs of circular bioeconomy was identified as important to drive growth. Another important aspect that was promoted was effective community engagement and this feeds back into the planning issue identified in the SWOT analysis. Effective community engagement could alleviate this barrier.

10. Regional Development Policy / Outcomes: The anticipated policy development requirements or benefits required to deliver the vision, include a cohesive regional circular bioeconomy policy within a defined roadmap or timeline, as well as further governance developments such as governance policies and models, best practice examples and Circular Bioeconomy Sector Standards.

The final result of the Southern Region of Ireland CBGMC is shown in Figure 38:

Figure 38. Southern Region of Ireland Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas

Žilina regional event

Žilina regional event organization

Kick-off meeting of circular bioeconomy stakeholders in ZSK

Figure 39. Save-the-date for the ZSK regional event

Regional customisation

The event was organised in Slovak language.

Regional partners followed the guidelines provided by the WP leaders.

The event was organized as a physical meeting. However, as one participant was not able to attend the meeting in person, he was connected online.

Invitations were sent based on previous discussion with local leaders. Representatives of Local Action Groups (LAGs) were invited to the workshop to co-create the “model” in collaboration with the Zilina Self-governing region representatives.

Representatives of organizations involved in the development of the Economic and Strategic Development Program (ESDP) were invited, too.

Several participants had moderate or low level of knowledge about bioeconomy, more time was dedicated to presentation and discussion about the pillars of the ESDP, its link to bioeconomy in local context.

Agenda

- 9:00 – 9:10 Opening
- 9:10 – 9:20 About ROBIN project
- 9:20 – 9:30 Survey (M&E online questionnaire)
- 9:30 – 9:45 Profile of the Žilina region
- 9:45 – 10:15 Discussion
- 10:15 – 11:45 Model creation together
- 11:45 – 12:00 Summary

Date, host, registration and venue

Date: 5 May, 2023, 9:00-12:00

Host: RAZSK

Registration: via google form

Venue: face-to-face

Figure 40. Moments from the co-creation workshop in Žilina region

Required equipment, material, logistics

Materials: Presentation about the project, brief profile of the region, SWOT analysis of the region, guidelines for filling up the canvas

Technical: laptop, projector, printed governance model canvas

Catering: light snacks – coffee, water, sandwiches, desserts

Participants

10 registered persons were representatives from different types of organisations:

- 2 policy makers,
- 1 representative of researcher and academic community,
- 4 civil society representatives and
- 1 business and SME representatives.
- 2 representatives of other stakeholders groups

Results from introductory session (project presentation + baseline monitoring survey)

The workshop was opened by a short welcome speech by the organizers and introduction of all participants.

In the next step, a short presentation about the project, its objectives and activities were provided. To set a common base, basic terms were mentioned to ensure all participants are familiar with them and mutual understanding is achieved.

The survey was then implemented via Mentimeter. As some participants arrived later, not all 10 answers were collected via Mentimeter. These answers are marked with * in the summary below.

Question 1: What is your current type of involvement in the regional bioeconomy sector?

a) I am a policymaker	2*
b) I am a researcher or academic	1*
c) I am a representative of the business community	1
d) I am a representative of a non-governmental or civil society organization	4
e) Other	2

Question 2: How long have you been working in your current position?

The majority of participants work in the position for at least 3 years.

a) Less than 3 years	0
b) 3 to 5 years	4*
c) 5 years and more	6*

Question 3: How well do you understand the concept of bioeconomy?

General understanding of the concept of bioeconomy varied considerably among participants.

Only 2 of the participants indicated they understand it very well or as experts.

a) I'm an expert	1
b) Very well	1
c) Moderately well	5*
d) Not well	2
e) Not at all	1

Question 4: How would you describe the level of development of the bioeconomy in your region?

As for the level of development of bioeconomy in the region, all participant agreed it is at moderate or limited level.

- | | |
|-----------------------------|----|
| a) Very advanced | 0 |
| b) Somewhat advanced | 0 |
| c) Moderate | 4* |
| d) Limited | 6* |
| e) Non-existent or very low | 0 |

Question 5: Significant improvements are needed in all 3 areas:

- Designing bioeconomy governance models and practices
- Implementation of governance models and practices
- Monitoring and evaluation of governance models and practices

Question 6: How effective do you think the current bioeconomy governance model is in achieving regional development goals?

As for the efficiency of the current bioeconomy governance model is in achieving regional development goals, participants see it as somewhat ineffective, very ineffective or even not applicable due to the non-existence of the model.

- | | |
|-------------------------|----|
| a) Very effective | 0 |
| b) Somewhat effective | 0 |
| c) Neutral | 0 |
| d) Somewhat ineffective | 5 |
| e) Very ineffective | 4* |
| f) Not applicable | 1 |

Question 7: What steps do you think can be taken to improve the effectiveness of regional bioeconomy governance models?

Participants also agreed all the below-mentioned steps are important in further development of the regional bioeconomy governance models.

- | | |
|--|-----|
| a) Increase funding for bioeconomy initiatives | 7* |
| b) Enhance stakeholder engagement | 8* |
| c) Streamline regulatory processes | 64* |
| d) Develop better infrastructure | 6 |
| e) Other (please specify) | 2 |

Additional ideas included: institutional cooperation, environmental education and awareness-raising, sustainably driven pilots as local examples of good practice.

Question 8: How well does your bioeconomy governance model promote sustainable development and environmental protection?

Participants also indicated the bioeconomy governance model is not very successful in promoting sustainable development and environmental protection.

- a) Very well 0
- b) Well 0
- c) Moderately 3*
- d) Poorly 7*
- e) Very poorly 0
- f) Not applicable 0

Question 9: How well does your bioeconomy governance model foster innovation and the development of new technologies and products in the bioeconomy sector?

When it comes to fostering innovation and the development of new technologies and products in the bioeconomy sector, the performance of the regions was also rated as poor.

- a) Very well 0
- b) Well 0
- c) Moderately 1
- d) Poorly 6*
- e) Very poorly 2*
- f) Not applicable 1

Question 10: How well does your region perform in identifying and grasping opportunities for innovative, sustainable circular business models in your region?

According to participants, the region performs poorly also in identifying and grasping opportunities for innovative, sustainable circular business models.

- a) Very well 0
- b) Well 0
- c) Moderately 0
- d) Poorly 8*
- e) Very poorly 2
- f) Not applicable 0

Question 11: How well does your region perform in developing social innovations addressing local needs?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a) Very well 0
- b) Well 0
- c) Moderately 2
- d) Poorly 7*
- e) Very poorly 1*
- f) Not applicable 0

Question 12: How well does the bioeconomy governance model ensure the participation and engagement of relevant stakeholders (e.g., government, business community, civil society, academia, local communities, etc.)?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a) Very effectively 0
- b) Effectively 0
- c) Moderately 2*
- d) Ineffectively 7*
- e) Very ineffectively 1
- f) Not applicable 0

Baseline monitoring survey results:

Question 1

Question 2

Question 3

Question 4

Question 5

Question 6

Question 7

Question 8

Question 9

Question 10

Question 11

Question 12

Figure 41. Žilina Baseline monitoring results

Results from session 1 (regional analysis: background, potential of biomass and SWOT analysis)

The session was opened by a presentation of the region's profile, developed based on the results of WP1 and regional strategic documents. The presentation was created in the form of a SWOT analysis, including information about:

- The main natural resources
- Types of feedstocks with the highest potential
- Most important economic sectors, their structure, main actors (producers, processing companies, supporting services, etc.)
- Main weaknesses, including the lack of bioeconomy strategy, inconsistency of policies, missing structures, as well as under-utilisation of the potential of the bioeconomy in the region due to ineffective or improper land use, production practices, etc.

Opportunities presented and discussed include creating an effective management model for different areas of the region development. Threats presented and also perceived by the participants stem from an inefficient governance model and lack of cooperation in the region, as well as changes caused e.g., by climate change.

Considerable part of the discussion was dedicated to the Economic and Strategic Development Program . In this section, people directly involved in the drafting of this document were mainly involved in the discussion. Not only the objectives set out in the document have been clarified, but in the absence of a separate bioeconomy strategy, the link of this document to the bioeconomy in the local context was explained.

This introduction is considered important because, as the initial data collection also showed, the awareness of some participants, who are perceived as some of the key actors in the next steps, is low.

At the same time, the authors stated that they have a vision of how to further support bioeconomy development in the region, but the “operational” level is not built yet.

The SWOT analysis was further expanded, based on the information gathered during the initial stage of the project. During the discussion, additional inputs were provided, resulting mainly from the Economic and Strategic Development Program of the Žilina region.

Results from session 2

The session was opened by a presentation of the canvas and its elements, followed by a facilitated discussion to fill in the template.

After the presentation, participants followed up on the discussion from part 1 – in this case several areas were mentioned that participants identified as key for further development of the bioeconomy in the region. Participants were invited to try to prioritise these areas. Initially, the discussion was mainly led by a representative of Žilina region and participants who participated in the creation of the Programme. In general, however, there was consensus, and the most important priority was agreed on - to ensure an integrated system of sustainable land use, supporting regional development by creating new business opportunities and jobs in the rural areas (for example supporting local farmers, new products and services, etc.), addressing environmental issues (such as addressing the issues of climate change, or negative effects of energy poverty), as well as addressing tackling social issues (for example by supporting social innovation and social economy).

Other parts of the canvas were also created as part of mutual discussion. Overall, it can be said that mainly Local Action Groups' (LAG) representatives were less active but did not object to the proposals.

From the discussion it was obvious that development objectives or priorities may vary from one territory to another, but the purpose of creating such a system is to create cooperation between the region, key actors in individual subregions, as well as representatives of the private sector, R&D and the general public.

The existing network of Local Action Groups and Regional Development Agencies (RRAs) is a good prerequisite for developing cooperation, but Local Action Groups activities in line with the Community-Led Local Development (CLLD) approach need to be supported and empower local leaders.

When it comes to the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas tool, it was very well received that the questions focused on Resources and Requirements do not include only funding.

However, the clear distinction between them was slightly unclear to participants. Despite the provided examples, some elements of the canvas needed to be discussed further and additional explanations provided. In result, some relevant items might be missing.

Satisfaction survey results

In general, we can say that the event was evaluated very positively. In most questions, participants rated 4 or 5 points (1 - Poor, 5 - Excellent).

A lower rating (3) was given by one participant in question 4 (Participation and dialogue with the audience).

One participant rated the usefulness of the REGIONAL GOVERNANCE CANVAS tool used in the event (Q5) as 2.

Question / Score	1	2	3	4	5
Q1: Organisation				2	8
Q2: Relevance of the topic and content				2	8
Q3: Technical Equipment				3	7

Q4: Participation and dialogue with the audience			1	4	4
Q5: Usefulness of the REGIONAL GOVERNANCE CANVAS tool used in the event		1		1	8

Žilina regional governance model

The context

The wealth of the Žilina region lies in natural resources, especially forests. More than 50% of the territory is covered by forests, there are 5 nature parks on the territory.

At the same time, however, the region is beginning to feel the effects of the climate crisis, as well as inappropriate interventions in the farming and forestry landscape.

For further development, it is perceived as a key use of the country's potential according to the specificities of individual sub-regions (e.g. nature parks as engines and not barriers to development) with the support of local communities.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>The Žilina region is the region with the highest entrepreneurial activity of young people and women in the Slovak Republic; Development of a pro-innovation and start-up environment.</p> <p>High priority of measures for water retention in the country expressed in the documents.</p> <p>Wealth of water resources</p> <p>High priority of the transition to a low carbon economy</p> <p>In the Žilina region there is a group of innovative companies that base their growth on research and development activities.</p> <p>In addition to industry, the local economy is based on exploiting the potential of forest and less agricultural landscapes and related traditional industries such as woodworking or sheep farming.</p> <p>Preserving traditions and crafts, reviving traditional events, traditional skills, ...</p> <p>Existence/preservation of local products; Extremely strong sense of identity in the natural regions of the region, localism.</p> <p>Examples of good cooperation between municipalities in the territory; Existence of public-private partnerships - LAGs and RRA.</p>	<p>Underdeveloped innovation potential; Insufficient support for entrepreneurship in some areas of business; Promoting services for micro-enterprises; Poor support for female entrepreneurship.</p> <p>Absence of preparation for the introduction of a circular economy system; Low interest of municipalities, the public and entrepreneurs in the application and creation of new products from waste recovery (reuse, upcycling, recycling).</p> <p>Consequences of collectivization of agriculture in the form of increased soil vulnerability and reduction of soil biodiversity, etc.; The consequences of long-term exceeded harvesting possibilities.</p> <p>Insufficient preparedness of Žilina region for the impacts of climate change, absence of adaptation strategy of the region.</p> <p>Abandonment of traditional farming (grazing, mowing...) and disappearance of associated species and habitats).</p> <p>Lack of low-carbon strategy of Žilina region; Lack of bioeconomy strategy.</p> <p>Lack of a strategy for environmental education, education, and awareness-raising.</p>

<p>A functioning municipal waste management system (excluding landfill capacity).</p>	<p>Poor support for small farms and artisans; Poor support for innovation in the region.</p> <p>Low share of agricultural land; Low agricultural land use rate.</p> <p>Low cooperation among territorial cooperation entities; Poor cooperation and support for rural youth due to lack of access to spaces and support for community activities Low level of cooperation of key actors to increase a comprehensive approach in solving social problems.</p> <p>Insufficient use of the LAGs instrument to activate rural cooperation; Not taking advantage of the experience and impact of the regional development agencies network; The practical absence of systemic cooperation and coordination of actors in the region.</p> <p>Low transfer of experience and examples of good practice from other regions and from abroad; Poor natural connectivity between urban agglomerations and the countryside.</p> <p>Unlinked conservation areas management programmes with local socio-economic development and tourism needs.</p>
<p>Opportunities</p>	<p>Threats</p>
<p>Targeted support of new promising sectors – healthy economic mix of the territory; Utilization of the entrepreneurial potential of seniors; promoting networking and cross-sectoral cooperation; family business in the countryside; Support for young people (also in rural areas) through specific activities (coworking, incubators, creative hobbies... in cultural and creative sectors, local economy...).</p> <p>Establishment and activities of the Regional Innovation Centre with a comprehensive offer of services for entrepreneurs; Supporting and promoting innovation in health, agriculture and social services; Support for pilot projects; possibility of drawing EU funds.</p> <p>Building a system of effective partnership – effective cooperation of stakeholders in solving employment.</p>	<p>Insufficient support for rural entrepreneurship; Adaptability and resilience of key sectors; Low support for social innovation; Low innovation capacity in some sub-regions and rural areas; Lack of a more comprehensive development strategy for the Region.</p> <p>Failure to exploit the potential of research and innovation infrastructure to increase the region's innovation capacity.</p> <p>Low participation of partners in the region in addressing employment.</p> <p>A non-systemic approach to addressing the circular economy at local and regional level; Lack of interest of SMEs and municipalities in cooperation in the field of circular economy.</p> <p>Increasing the risk of local floods, other extreme weather events and impacts as a result of climate change.</p>

<p>Transition to circular economy, especially the prevention and minimization of waste generation, including the reuse of products, reduction of the share of landfilling of waste and increase of their material and energy use.</p> <p>Promoting adaptation measures to the impacts of climate change.</p> <p>Increasing the share of RES in energy production and using collaborative energy in the management of surplus energy.</p> <p>Tapping the potential for sustainable land use - Integrated land management, in particular through integrated spatial planning (National parks as an "engine" of regional development). It includes sectoral (forestry, water and agriculture, nature protection, urbanization, recreation, energy, etc.), territorial (vertical and horizontal) and organizational integration.</p> <p>Existing potential for the development of small businesses; Creation of local networks of producers; The development of a network of local stores (chains) - so far only hints.</p> <p>High share of forest land in the region as a prerequisite for the development of forestry and secondary wood processing; Increasing the share of agroecology.</p> <p>Social economy (addressing local public needs and inclusion).</p> <p>Activating and participating the public in public affairs; Use of the CLLD approach.</p> <p>Established cross-border partnerships; Strengthening urban-rural cooperation; Establishment of a system of cooperation and coordination of actors; Drawing on experience, good practice and projection of international development concepts (different agendas) for regional, urban and rural development.</p>	<p>Increasing economic pressure causing the incineration of low-quality fuels and waste in households.</p> <p>Absence of adaptive and integrated management of habitats, ecosystems and landscapes; Expansion of urbanization and landscape "islands of heat"; Continuation of trends of unsuitable large-scale farming; Low resilience and adaptability of ecosystems to climate change impacts in the landscape; Reduction of area and quality of forests; water resources.</p> <p>Lack of awareness of the population in protecting and solving environmental problems; Chemical pollution from human activities.</p> <p>The unpreparedness of the Žilina region may have a significant impact on the requirements of the Green Deal and related EU upcoming steps in the field of reducing impacts on climate, adaptation to the impacts of climate change, biodiversity protection, etc.</p> <p>Continued depopulation - an exodus of young and talented people outside the territory; Dysfunctional and unsustainable system of state support for regional development entities. Weakening the "status" and number of regionalists in urban, local and rural development; Non-conceptual approach of the state to the coordination of regional development, the practical absence of systemic financial instruments; No system of capacity preparation for regional, urban and rural development.</p>
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Identification of the regional Governance Model improvement areas

In the absence of a strategic document for bioeconomy, discussions were aimed at defining the first steps for creating a model supporting sustainable regional development based on the principles of circular (bio)economy.

Sustainable use of natural assets (e.g. nature parks as an engine for development), taking into account climate impacts, economic development and social issues was at the heart of the discussions.

The selected improvement area as main goal to achieve within the ROBIN project at regional level, to which the action plans to be developed in T2.2. should be addressed to, is focused on the development of a model supporting integrated territorial development based on the principles of circular (bio)economy. Although this goal is formulated in the Programme of Economic and Social Development of Žilina region, participants agreed that both at the regional and lower levels it is not clearly defined how to operationalize this model – for example subjects and their roles, relationship management, processes, priorities and activities, etc.

The priorities discussed included:

- **A system of rational land use based on the principles of circular bioeconomy**
- Creating a model for the development of national parks as engines of regional development
- Energy self-sufficiency with the use of renewable resources in individual sub-regions
- Developing a circular economy in the region
- Support for rural regions, including support for local farmers, production of local products – linked to preserving and strengthening cultural identity

During the discussion, participants agreed that there was one major goal identified (A system of rational land use based on the principles of circular bioeconomy) and the other priorities present partial issues that can be covered by this more general objective.

Detailed prioritisation of these partial issues has not been carried out as priorities may vary from sub-region to sub-region. The establishment of the system should provide scope for identifying priorities for sub-regions and taking action at sub-regional level.

Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Results

REGIONAL VISION / VALUE PROPOSITION

- A system of rational land use based on the principles of circular bioeconomy
- One of the main actions defined in the Economic and Social Development Programme is Creation of Regional Circular Centres

Environmental benefits:

- Mitigating the impacts of climate change
- Improvement of air quality in the region
- Sustainable use of natural resources with respect to socio-economic development needs

Economic benefits

- National parks as engines of regional development
- Increasing food sovereignty
- Increasing energy self-sufficiency
- New business opportunities in rural and urban areas
- Creation, further development of local value chains
- Creating a collaborative economy in the region

Social benefits

- Capacity development at regional level

- Contributing to improved population health
- Creating new opportunities for vulnerable groups
- Building regional identity and value

ACTIVITIES

1. Identification of key actors in the region - project promoters - change agents
2. Identify potential for collaboration and prioritisation (Identify key areas where activities and funding could be directed)
3. Develop Local Action Group activities (LEADER Programme) - not to play only an administrative role
4. Communication, involvement, developing relationships with actors, networking
5. Developing a plan for pilot actions and their implementation
6. Capacity building in the region in specific areas
7. Identifying examples of good and bad practice from Slovakia
8. Implementation of awareness raising and education activities
9. Improve planning
10. Monitoring and evaluation tools and processes

PARTNERSHIPS

- Local Action Groups - LEADER programme
- Clusters
- Innovation Network

RESOURCES

- Natural resources in the region
- Preserving traditions and crafts, reviving traditional events, traditional skills
- Innovation actors
- Existing financial resources of ŽSK and other financial resources (EU programmes, etc.)

INFRASTRUCTURE

Not applicable

REGIONAL ACTORS

- Local action groups
- Key actors of the so called "Regions of Strategic-Planning" (according to the definitions of the European Commission and OECD, sub-territorial units for planning at sub-regional level, which can be understood as groups of municipalities for the purpose of supporting regional development)
- Actors involved in the Integrated strategy for Sustainable Urban Development
- Innovation Centre innovia, other innovation leaders
- Leaders in the sub-regions, active citizens
- Organisations active in the field of environmental education

RELATIONSHIPS

- A participatory approach to system building
- Collaboration with local leaders in the implementation of activities
- Communication with stakeholders
- Communication with the wider public

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

- Events
- Internal meetings of the community
- e-mail communication
- Communication through partners - e.g. schools, Local Action Groups
- Online: social networks, websites

REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT REQUIREMENTS

- Staff capacity at multiple levels - coordination, planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation
- Empowered local leaders
- Financial resources to implement the objectives
- Development of collaborative economy
- Environmental education and awareness-raising
- Effective exchange of knowledge and experience from other regions and from abroad
- Supporting regions from the state level (e.g., competencies in the hands of regions)

REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT POLICY / OUTCOMES

Operationalization Plan of the Integrated System of Sustainable Land Use (Regional Circular Economy Centre)

Figure 42. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas resulting from the co-creation workshop in the Žilina Region

4. Conclusions

As planned, the ROBIN regional co-creation workshops reached their main goals of:

- a) engage the regional ecosystems (mainly through the MARC members) in the co-creation of governance models and practices that could overcome barriers and seize opportunities for circular bioeconomy at regional level.
- b) Serve as first testing scenarios for the CBGMG continuous improvement process

As expected, a total of five workshops have been held between May and June 2023, one in each ROBIN region, gathering in total 69 relevant actors from the different regional ecosystems and MARCs.

- 15 policy makers,
- 17 researchers and academics,
- 12 civil society representatives,
- 23 business and SME representatives.
- 2 Other

Each region has identified a value proposition and created a new or improved regional governance model linked to it, to work in and transform into a business model during the next work package activity (T2.2.), when dedicated action plans will be developed, including social activities and measures among others, considering typologies of governance models and good practices gathered in ROBIN deliverables D1.1. and D1.2, respectively.

In each workshop a value proposition has been selected to build a dedicated governance business model based on the CBGMG per region (a total of 5), and more than 50 activities identified in total (51), to feed the regional Support Action Plans to be performed in T2.2., including social measures aligned with the social benefits identified per regional value proposition.

All the work performed at regional level has followed a two-fold approach:

- Observing common and agreed general indications to guarantee that the workshops' main objectives were reached,
- Adapting the content and co-creation experience to each region maturity level and specific needs (including information about the regional situation framework, resource available and SWOT analysis)

The development of the co-creation activities were nurtured by the results obtained in ROBIN's work package 1, specially by the Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models (D1.1.) and its Governance Models Typology Matrix, and the Good Governance Practices (D1.2.). Both documents will be also used in the additional development of activities under WP2, namely the creation of the business models and actions plans for the operational planification of the regional governance models developed in T2.1.

In general, according to the satisfaction surveys, the workshops were valued very positively with **high marks** in all categories.

The CBGMC, that will be part of the ROBIN Toolbox, was used as a prototype, and **some valuable comments towards the potential improvement of the tool were also gathered.**

Table 5. Main workshops results

Region	Andalusia	Baden-Württemberg	Central Macedonia	Southern Region	Žilina
Participants	14	10	22	13	10
Regional value proposition	Consolidation of the sector through the creation of a regional circular bioeconomy node	Improving the Funding / Financing	Development of Bioeconomy Cluster in Central Macedonia with all actors	A Working Document to inform Regional Circular Bioeconomy & Structures	A system of rational land use based on the principles of circular bioeconomy Creation of Regional Circular Centres
Activities	1. Update of the regional situation diagnosis.	1. Development of the bioeconomy strategy in BW (Bioeconomy Strategy 2.0)	1. Opening event of the cluster	1. Establish Steering Committee > Collaboration on document.	1. Identification of key actors in the region - project promoters - change agents
	2. Prospective analysis of relevant actors.	2. Further development of funding instruments to support industrialisation (e.g., risk capital credit, sector-specific funding)	2. Search for financing tools and member information.	2. Engage Bioeconomy Stakeholders > Coordination map / framework.	2. Identify potential for collaboration and prioritisation (Identify key areas where activities and funding could be directed)
	3. Involvement of key stakeholders and strategic members of the quadruple helix.	3. Creation of more matchmaking opportunities between stakeholders related to collaboration in public funded projects	3. Creation of a digital platform.	3. Education Building > Mapping & Review of current landscape	3. Develop Local Action Group activities (LEADER Programme) - not to play only an administrative role
	4. Alignment with regional strategies.	4. New funding instruments for scaling-up	4. Promotion (marketing campaign) of energy communities.	4. Engage with Local Authorities > Review / gaps in engagement.	4. Communication, involvement, developing relationships with actors, networking
	5. Development of a 3-5 year strategic plan.	5. Define target groups	5. Recruitment of various members.	5. Bioeconomy Awareness > Develop outreach plan (bioeconomy week).	5. Developing a plan for pilot actions and their implementation
	6. Identification of resources needed for the creation and implementation of the node.	6. Further development of life cycle assessment/environmental footprint assessment via funding instruments	6. Development of a strategic vision.	6. Regional Bioeconomy research > Identify underutilized research areas.	6. Capacity building in the region in specific areas

7. Development of a multi-annual action plan.	7. Set an evaluation system for bioeconomy innovations (e.g., economic viability assessment) for financial decisions	7. Establishment of an office for specialization in bioeconomy.	7. Business/SME Bioeconomy> Identify matchmaking opportunities.	7. Identifying examples of good and bad practice from Slovakia
8. Study of the annualised budget, identification of possible sources of funds and analysis of financing opportunities.	8. Match co-financing with year-round application phase	8. Establishment of a joint venture between the partners of the cluster.	8. Bioeconomy Funding assist > Identify underutilized funding mechanisms.	8. Implementation of awareness raising and education activities
9. Development of a 3-5 year economic-financial viability model for the node, based on the established strategic plan.		9. Establishment of educational programs.	9. Evaluate Governance Structures / Policies suitable for Southern Region.	9. Improve planning
10. Development of a communication plan for the node, including its mission, vision and a work plan to improve its image, positioning, and visibility.		10. Definition of a regional information and training plan focusing on targeting and mentoring (consultancy).	10. Strategy Implementation > Examination of level (nuts 2/nuts 3).	10. Monitoring and evaluation tools and processes
11. Campaign to raise awareness and attract members.				
12. Analysis of the best legal instrument for the constitution of the node (agreements, statutes)				
13. Establishment of the node and its organisational structure.				

5. Annexes

Annex 1: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Workshop Guide

Bioeconomy Pillars.....	3
1. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Work Draft Canvas.....	4
1.1 Canvas Sections.....	4
1.1.1 Regional Vision / Value Proposition.....	4
1.1.2 Activities.....	5
1.1.3 Partnerships.....	5
1.1.4 Resources.....	5
1.1.5 Infrastructure.....	5
1.1.6 Regional Actors / Stakeholder.....	5
1.1.7 Regional Relationships.....	5
1.1.8 Channels.....	6
1.1.9 Regional Development Requirements.....	6
1.1.10 Regional Development Policy / Outcomes.....	6
2. Notes.....	7
2.1 Co-Creation Tool.....	7
2.2 Canvas Progression.....	7
2.3 Draft Canvas.....	7
3. Appendix.....	8
3.1 Facilitators Canvas Workshop Feedback Form.....	8

Figure 43. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Workshop Guide

Bioeconomy Pillars

The ethos of the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas is based upon the EU Bioeconomy Pillars, these five pillars should be kept in mind when completing the canvas during the workshop particularly when considering the support activities and constructing the Regional Action Plans.

Figure 44. EU Bioeconomy Pillars

1. Ensuring Food and Nutrition Security
2. Managing Natural Resources Sustainably
3. Reducing dependence on non-renewable unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad.
4. Mitigating and adapting to climate change.

5. Strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs.

Further information regarding the Bioeconomy Pillars can be found : [here](#)

Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Work Draft Canvas

Figure 45. Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas Work Draft Canvas

Canvas Sections - Recommended Progression

Regional Vision / Value Proposition

Core to the workshop exercise, the regional vision should be seen as the component that brings the sections on the left of the canvas into focus towards a defined regional vision / value proposition. This will vary from region to region, but may include an integrated regional bioeconomy, a functioning regional governance structure etc. In establishing the regional vision, the following aspects should be considered:

- Environmental Benefits – Cleaner atmosphere, better waste management, etc...
- Economic Benefits – Smart Specializations, Attract & retain young talent in the region, etc...
- Social Benefits – Improved level of societal health, reduction of energy poverty, etc...

Activities

Activities describes the supporting activities or actions which will be required to implement the regional vision and will input to the regional action plan. Areas such as increasing stakeholder engagement, developing regional bioeconomy business plans, implementing environmental protection plans, or increasing bioeconomy skills development are some activities that could be considered, and these will be specific and unique to each region. 10 or more support activities should be developed within each regional workshop.

Partnerships

Partnerships describes the actors within the region that are required to collaborate to execute the regional vision. These may include Regional and Local Authorities, Civil Society, Research Institutes etc. The quadruple helix or penta helix model is a good indicator to guide for this section within the region.

Resources

The describes the unique resources that are available to each specific region that that can be harnessed to align with the development the regional bioeconomy. This will include the availability of biological resources, innovations, and R & D (and knowhow) within the region.

Infrastructure

Within this draft canvas, infrastructure has been allocated its own segment, separate from other resources. This covers the existing infrastructure which could be used to support the development of the bioeconomy such as pilot plants, industrial bio-refineries or bioenergy plants, or other existing relevant industrial infrastructure.

Regional Actors / Stakeholder

This section relates to those within the region that are involved in delivering the regional vision / value proposition. Again, the quadruple helix / penta helix model of actors within Environment, Education & Research, Government, Civil Society, and Industry should be considered and utilised.

input on the requirements for communicating the main messages of the regional vision and building relationships with the primary actors involved.

Regional Relationships

Regional relationships will explore how the relationships with the Regional Actors / Stakeholders will be developed towards delivering the regional vision / value proposition. This could include community building initiatives, co-creation activities between different relevant stakeholders, clustering etc.

Channels

Channels describes how the message will be communicated to the wider audience or actors/stakeholders who are not directly involved in creating the regional vision or how does the information about the regional vision / value proposition get to the outside world. Examples include social media, information events, a regional central resource portal, policy framework application, website with information on a well governed region etc...

Regional Development Requirements

Regional development requirements are the first of the aspects that will explore how the regional vision will work. In this instance it is centred on the 'cost' involved to successfully implement the

vision. Examples may include provision of regional support, availability of an educated work force, circular bioeconomy education etc...

Regional Development Policy / Outcomes

Regional Development Policy is the policy development requirements or benefits required to deliver the regional vision. Regional Development Policy is the 'revenue' that the region will see as an outcome of regional support activities, regional vision and all the other aspects combined. From a policy perspective this "revenue" may include aspects such as governance structure, action plans, policies etc.

Notes

Co-Creation Tool

The Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas should be seen as a strategic co-creation tool that will allow each region to describe, design, challenge and invent a regional vision, and identify support activities required to implement this vision. This will be specific to each region. This tool can be continuously updated as the region's circular bioeconomy develops.

Canvas Progression

Whilst it is intended that completion of the canvas be done left to right (except for supporting activities, which may be identified after the vision has been identified), we advise that as subsequent sections of the canvas are completed, others are revisited and adjusted as required.

Draft Canvas

The Robin T2.1 workshops will be the initial testing of this canvas. A template for capturing feedback of the overall effectiveness of the canvas and recommended adjustments arising from use within the workshops will be provided.

Annex 2 - Baseline questionnaire

Questionnaire for an online survey (using tools such as Mentimeter or an online questionnaire that can be sent to participants in advance¹)

Question 1:

What is your current type of involvement in the regional bioeconomy sector?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a. I am a policymaker
- b. I am a researcher or academic
- c. I am a representative of the business community
- d. I am a representative of a non-governmental or civil society organization
- e. Other

Question 2:

How long have you been working in your current position?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a. Less than 3 years
- b. 3 to 5 years
- c. 5 years and more

Question 3:

How well do you understand the concept of bioeconomy?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a. I'm an expert
- b. Very well
- c. Moderately well
- d. Not well
- e. Not at all

Question 4:

How would you describe the level of development of the bioeconomy in your region?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a. Very advanced
- b. Somewhat advanced
- c. Moderate
- d. Limited
- e. Non-existent or very low

Question 5:

How would you rate the level of your region in:

- Designing bioeconomy governance models and practices
- Implementation of governance models and practices
- Monitoring and evaluation of governance models and practices

Scale -2 -1 0 1 2 (-2 very ineffective, -1 ineffective, 0 neutral, 1 effective, 2 very effective)

Question 6:

How effective do you think the current bioeconomy governance model is in achieving regional development goals?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a. Very effective
- b. Somewhat effective
- c. Neutral
- d. somewhat ineffective
- e. Very ineffective
- f. Not applicable

Question 7:

What steps do you think can be taken to improve the effectiveness of regional bioeconomy governance models?

Multiple choice: several answers possible

- a. Increase funding for bioeconomy initiatives
- b. Enhance stakeholder engagement
- c. Streamline regulatory processes
- d. Develop better infrastructure
- e. Other (please specify)

Question 8:

How well does your bioeconomy governance model promote sustainable development and environmental protection?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a. Very well
- b. Well
- c. Moderately
- d. Poorly
- e. Very poorly
- f. Not applicable

Question 9:

How well does your bioeconomy governance model foster innovation and the development of new technologies and products in the bioeconomy sector?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a. Very well
- b. Well
- c. Moderately
- d. Poorly
- e. Very poorly
- f. Not applicable

Question 10:

How well does your region perform in identifying and grasping opportunities for innovative, sustainable circular business models in your region?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a. Very well
- b. Well

- c. Moderately
- d. Poorly
- e. Very poorly

Question 11:

How well does your region perform in developing social innovations addressing local needs?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a. Very well
- b. Well
- c. Moderately
- d. Poorly
- e. Very poorly

Question 12:

How well does the bioeconomy governance model ensure the participation and engagement of relevant stakeholders (e.g., government, business community, civil society, academia, local communities, etc.)?

Multiple choice: one answer

- a. Very effectively
- b. Effectively
- c. Moderately
- d. Ineffectively
- e. Very ineffectively
- f. Not applicable

Question 13:

Do you know or use some efficient tools that can be used when designing, implementing or monitoring bioeconomy governance models? Please provide some examples.

Short answer – cloud

Annex 3 – Scheme of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework

Figure 46. Scheme of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework

Annex 4 - List of actions of the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Framework

1. Ensuring Food and Nutrition Security

1.1 Food security and nutrition are supported.

- 1.1.a Availability
- 1.1.b Access 1 Ensuring Food and Nutrition Security
- 1.1.c Utilisation 1 Ensuring Food and Nutrition Security
- 1.1.d Stability 1 Ensuring Food and Nutrition Security

1.2 Local economies, societies and environmental conditions of countries exporting food to the EU are not hampered but rather harnessed by the trade of raw and processed biomass and related technologies.

- 1.2.a Economic impact of trade in exporting countries of food (to EU)
- 1.2.b Environmental footprints in exporting countries of food (to EU)
- 1.2.c Social impact of trade in exporting countries of food (to EU)

2. Managing Natural Resources Sustainably.

2.1 Ecosystem capacity to produce services is maintained or enhanced.

- 2.1.a Environmental quality
- 2.1.b Structural and functional ecosystem attributes
- 2.1.d Species diversity and abundance
- 2.1.e Conservation status of habitats and species

2.2 Primary production sectors are managed sustainably.

- 2.2.a Pressures from Forest Management
- 2.2.b Pressures from marine fisheries & aquaculture management
- 2.2.c Pressures from freshwater fisheries & aquaculture management
- 2.2.d Pressures from agroecosystems

2.3 Ecosystem services contribution to human well-being is maintained or enhanced.

- 2.3.a Provisioning services.
- 2.3.b Regulating services.
- 2.3.c Cultural services

3. Reducing dependence on non-renewable unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad.

3.1 Resource efficiency, waste prevention and waste-re-use along the whole bioeconomy value chain is improved.

- 3.1.a Resource efficiency (Material footprint)
- 3.1.b Energy efficiency 3 Reducing dependence on non-renewable unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad.
- 3.1.c Biogenic waste prevention, re-use/recycling, and recovery

3.2 Food loss and waste is minimised and, when unavoidable, its biomass is reused or recycled.

- 3.2.a Food loss and waste minimization

3.3 Bioeconomy should promote sustainable production and consumption of biomass and bio-based products (within EU)

- 3.3.a Bio-based products environmental impacts

3.4 Consumption patterns of bioeconomy goods match sustainable supply levels of biomass.

- 3.4.a Consumption and demand for biomass and bio-based products
- 3.4.b Production of bio-based products
- 3.4.c Reduced dependence on non-renewable resources

3.5 Local economies of countries exporting non-food commodities to the EU are not hampered but rather harnessed by the trade of raw and processed biomass and related technologies.

- 3.5.a Economic impact of trade in exporting countries of non-food (to EU)
- 3.5.b Environmental footprints in exporting countries of non-food (to EU)
- 3.5.c Social impact of trade in exporting countries of non-food (to EU)

3.6 The sustainability of urban centres is enhanced.

- 3.6.a Enhanced well-being and health of urban dwellers

4. Mitigating and adapting to climate change.

- 4.1 *Climate change mitigation and adaptation are pursued.*
 - 4.1.a Climate change mitigation
 - 4.1.b Climate change adaptation
- 4.2 *The sustainability of urban centres is enhanced.*
 - 4.2.a Enhanced resilience/adaptation to climate change for urban areas
- 5. Strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs.**
 - 5.1 *Economic development is fostered.*
 - 5.1.a Contribution of bioeconomy to economic development
 - 5.1.b Value of raw and processed biomass, value added in bioeconomy sectors.
 - 5.1.c Exports of EU food and non-food biomass processed goods and/or related technologies.
 - 5.1.d Comparative advantage 5 Strengthening
 - 5.2 *Inclusive economic growth is strengthened.*
 - 5.2.a Employment in bioeconomy
 - 5.2.b Working conditions related to bioeconomy.
 - 5.2.c Equality & inclusiveness in bioeconomy sectors
 - 5.3 *Resilience of the rural, coastal, and urban economy is enhanced.*
 - 5.3.a Physical infrastructure (accessibility, services)
 - 5.3.c Bioeconomy investments in rural & coastal areas
 - 5.3.d Rural income diversification
 - 5.3.e Income of primary producers
 - 5.4 *Existing knowledge is adequately valued, and proven sound technologies are fostered.*
 - 5.4.a Existing knowledge on bioeconomy technologies
 - 5.5 *Knowledge generation and innovation are promoted.*
 - 5.5.a Knowledge generation/ (high level) education
 - 5.5.b Research and innovation
 - 5.6 *Demand and supply-side market mechanisms and policy coherence between supply and demand of food and non-food goods are enhanced.*
 - 5.6.a Market mechanisms (e.g., prices, consumer awareness) 5 Strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs.
 - 5.6.c Resource competition among sectors of the bioeconomy and Biomass demand for new value chains
- 6. Social Benefits**
 - 6.1. Improved Level of Health
 - 6.2. Increased Local Employment
 - 6.3. Reduction of Energy Poverty
 - 6.4. Social Enterprises with local communities benefit from environmental protection, employment generation and community development.
 - 6.5. Inclusion of the most disadvantaged sectors or those with difficulties in accessing the labour market.
 - 6.6. Gender Equality
- 7. Environmental Benefits**
 - 7.1. Cleaner atmosphere
 - 7.2. Proper / improved waste management
 - 7.3. Protection of Biodiversity
 - 7.4. Alignment with key Climate Action Goals
- 8. Regional Benefits**
 - 8.1. Development of a diverse base of smart economic specialisms across regions
 - 8.2. Attract and retain young talent in the region.
 - 8.3. Engagement with regional stakeholders across government, academia, community & industry.

Annex 5 - Satisfaction survey template

With the aim of gathering information about your experience at the [Name of the event], we have created this survey. Your input will help us in the planning and implementation of future activities.

This survey will take no longer than 5 minutes. Thank you very much for your collaboration.

*Mandatory

Please, evaluate the following aspects of the event:

- Organisation *
From 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent)
- Relevance of the topic and content *
From 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent)
- Level of the speakers (quality and clarity) *
From 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent)
- Participation and dialogue with the audience *
From 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent)
- Where did you hear about this event?
 - Social Media
 - e-mail / Newsletter
 - EU Green Week website
 - Direct invitation
 - Other: ...
- Usefulness of the REGIONAL GOVERNANCE CANVAS tool used in the event
From 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent)

Please, write below any comment or feedback about the event and/or the tool.

.....

Thank you!

If the event is done face-to-face, an additional question related to the location and catering can be included.

Annex 6 - Official agenda Central Macedonia workshop

ΠΕΡΙΦΕΡΕΙΑ ΚΕΝΤΡΙΚΗΣ ΜΑΚΕΔΟΝΙΑΣ

ΑΡΙΣΤΟΤΕΛΕΙΟ
ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ
ΘΕΣΣΑΛΟΝΙΚΗΣ

Περιφερειακό Εργαστήριο Συνδημιουργίας

Πέμπτη 8 Ιουνίου 2023

ΔΕΘ - Περίπτερο 15 (ΙΣΟΓΕΙΟ | Stand:C07)

Ωρα	
10.00 – 10.10	Καλωσόρισμα και εισαγωγή Μια σύντομη παρουσίαση του ευρωπαϊκού έργου ROBIN και των κύριων στόχων του εργαστηρίου
10.10 – 10.25	Βιοοικονομία - Περιφερειακό πλαίσιο Παρουσίαση του περιφερειακού τοπίου της Βιοοικονομίας, του μοντέλου περιφερειακής διακυβέρνησης και ανάλυση SWOT
10.25 – 10.45	Διαδραστικό Εργαστήριο – 1 Περιφερειακό Πλαίσιο Οι συμμετέχοντες μοιράζονται τις απόψεις τους σχετικά με το περιφερειακό πλαίσιο
10.45 – 11.00	Διάλειμμα για καφέ
11.00 – 11.15	Διαδραστικό Εργαστήριο – 2 Ορισμός των περιοχών βελτίωσης Ιεράρχηση των δράσεων για τη στήριξη της μετάβασης στη Βιοοικονομία
11.15 – 11.50	Διαδραστικό Εργαστήριο – 3 Προσχέδιο Διακυβέρνησης Συνδημιουργία του περιφερειακού καμβά διακυβέρνησης για τη Βιοοικονομία
11.50 – 12.00	Ανακεφαλαίωση – Συμπεράσματα Τα επόμενα βήματα του ROBIN, οι δράσεις που προγραμματίζονται σε περιφερειακό επίπεδο και έρευνα ικανοποίησης
12.00 – 13.00	Συνάντηση Περιφερειακής Ομάδας Υποστήριξης του έργου “CITISYSTEM” - Supporting cities in sustainable biobased systemic change”

Funded by
the European Union

CITISYSTEM

Figure 47. Official agenda Central Macedonia workshop

Annex 7 - Central Macedonia Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas

Figure 48. Central Macedonia Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas

About the project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures in to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. We demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. We set-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the CCRI-CSO. We also provide them with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process we coordinate our actions with the CCRI-CSO.

Partners	URL
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	www.qplan-intl.gr
FUNDACION CORPORACION TECHNOLOGICA SE ANDALUCIA	www.corporaciontecnologica.com
WHITE RESEARCH SRL	www.white-research.eu
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	www.pedal-consulting.eu
STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	www.steinbeis-europa.de
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CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	www.juntadeandalucia.es
INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA	www.juntadeandalucia.es
BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTEMBERG GMBH	www.bio-pro.de
SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	www.southernassembly.ie

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